

Abstract

Mathematical expression extraction is a problem with many applications in the digitization process. To implement a complete mathematical expression extraction system, two subproblems need to be solved, including the problem of detecting mathematical expression regions and the problem of recognizing mathematical expressions.

Among the two aforementioned problems, mathematical expression recognition is considered a challenging task, and currently, existing methods for this problem still have many limitations that need to be improved. The goal of this problem is to determine the content of mathematical expressions and convert them from image format into a digital form that can be stored on electronic devices. This problem has particularly high applicability in the current context of digital transformation, especially in the fields of science and education. Therefore, mathematical expression recognition has been receiving increasing attention from the global artificial intelligence research community in recent years.

In this thesis, our objective is to research and develop an efficient model for the MER problem, and then combine it with mathematical expression detection models published by prior research, to complete a comprehensive mathematical expression extraction system.

We proposed a model based on the Seq2seq architecture, incorporating the Vision Transformer architecture for the context modeling component. Experiments on public datasets have confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed method. Additionally, recognizing the data limitations in MER research motivated us to construct a new dataset called LIMD with the hope of replacing the current public dataset. Finally, we completed the extraction system by combining the Hybrid Vision Transformer model with the ScanSSD model [1], a mathematical expression region detection model. The entire source code and dataset will be publicly available on

GitHub¹.

¹<https://github.com/duylebkHCM/doc2tex>

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Glossary & Abbreviations

MER	Mathematical Expression Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
STR	Scene Text Recognition
DNN	Deep Neural Network
FC	Fully Connected
CNN	Convolution Neural Network
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
GNN	Graph Neural Network
FFN	Feed-forward-network
MLP	Multi Layer Perceptron
Seq2seq	Sequence to sequence
ViT	Vision Transformer
LSTM	Long short term memory
VGG	Visual Geometry Group
BiLSTM	Bidirectional Long short-term memory
SOTA	State-of-the-art
MLE	Maximum likelihood estimation

MHSA Multi-Head Self-Attention

WYGIWYS . What You Get Is What You See

PDF Portable document format

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

With the rapid development of science and technology today, technological devices have gradually become an indispensable part of the daily lives of every organization and individual in society. This has contributed to changes in the way people interact with each other in their daily work. This change is also known by another popular name in recent years: the “Digital Transformation Wave.” The impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic acted as a catalyst, accelerating this wave. This is considered an inevitable trend that has been and continues to affect most fields in Vietnam, including two particularly important areas: science and education. When discussing digital transformation in science and education, one cannot overlook the need to digitize a large volume of books, newspapers, and printed documents into digital formats such as PDF, Word, etc., for the purpose of long-term storage and easier dissemination of knowledge. Document digitization also aids in extracting information from components within documents, thereby enabling the utilization of collected information for various purposes. In the field of science, most types of documents such as books, scientific papers, and specialized journals contain components that need to be extracted, including data tables, illustrations, charts, and mathematical formulas. This information can be used for retrieval systems, text summarization, or question-answering systems. In the field of education, data digitization can help teachers reduce the burden of teaching through automatic grading systems based on data from student examinations.

As can be seen, digital transformation plays an important role in the develop-

(The moduli spaces $M_{g,n}$ are only well-defined for $g \geq 3$, the exceptional case $M_{1,3}$ equals $M_{0,4}$ and is thus one-dimensional.) Moduli spaces are not everywhere-smooth, since surfaces with orientable higher symmetry give rise to so-called orbifold points.

One way to think about the complex structure on Σ is as the conformal class of a metric h_g . Indeed, a metric defines a complex structure through

$$J_g^2 = -\text{Id}_{T\Sigma} \otimes \text{Id}_{T\Sigma}^*$$

with Id the identity on the tangent bundle, and Id is a useful fact that all J_g can be obtained in this way. Since the definition of J is independent of local rescalings of h_g , we can represent $M_{g,n}$ alternately as the space of metrics modulo local rescalings and diffeomorphisms.

The moduli space $M_{g,n}$ has a boundary and there exists a direct, intuitive interpretation of the points in the boundary — they represent degenerate surfaces. There are basically two ways in which a surface can degenerate. If we think in terms of a conformal class of metrics, the surface can either form a node — or, equivalently, a long neck — or two marked points can collide. The boundary of $M_{g,n}$ can be thought of to be at infinity. One would like to compactify the moduli space by adding points at infinity, one could here use compactification the plane \mathbb{R}^2 to the n -dimensional sphere. In this case the points at infinity represent particular Riemann surfaces. The Deligne-Mumford or ‘stable’ compactification [7] adds three types of these points, as is illustrated in Fig. 2.

(i) The process in which two points x_1 and x_2 ‘collide’ if $g = x_1 = x_2$ tends to zero can (after a coordinate transformation $x' = x/g$) alternately be described as the process in which a sphere, that contains x_1 and x_2 at fixed distance, pinches off the surface by forming a neck of length g . These two descriptions are fully equivalent, but the latter is actually more in the spirit of conformal field theory, since we are in an obvious way the operator product expansion regime. It is also suggestive of another end point configuration. Here the natural final configuration is not simply the surface with $x_1 = x_2$, but it consists of a separate sphere containing the points x_1, x_2 and a third point where the infinite long tube was attached, together with the original surface with one marked point less. In the stable compactification we add this configuration as limit point, which equivalently can be written as the process

$$(g, x) \rightarrow (g, x - 1) + (0, 3). \quad (2.3)$$

Recall that the three-punctured sphere has a unique complex structure, so there are no moduli associated to it and this boundary component has codimension one. The crucial property of this compactification is that the points x_i never come together. The two other degeneration modes are more straightforward.

(ii) If a circle of non-trivial homology pinches, we replace the surface by a surface with one handle less and two extra marked points — the attachment points of the vanishing disk

handle:

$$(g, x) \rightarrow (g - 1, x + 2) \quad (2.4)$$

(iii) In a similar spirit, in case of dividing cycle pinches, the resulting surface consists of two disconnected surfaces of genus g' and g'' , each having one extra puncture

$$(g, x) \rightarrow (g', x' + 1) + (g'', x'' + x' + 1) \quad (2.5)$$

It can be shown that this prescription makes $M_{g,n}$ into a compact smooth (orbifold) space $\bar{M}_{g,n}$. We now want to consider its cohomology ring $H^*(\bar{M}_{g,n})$. A particular set of elements has been considered by Mumford, Morita, and Miller [25, 26]. These classes are constructed as follows [7]. There exist n natural line bundles L_1, \dots, L_n on the moduli space. The fiber of the bundle L_i at a point $\Sigma \in M_{g,n}$ is the complex space of the point x_i on the surface Σ . These line bundles have first Chern classes that in de Rham cohomology are represented by the curvature F_i of an arbitrary $U(1)$ connection on L_i . This defines for us the $2n$ -dimensional classes

$$\sigma_i(i) = c_1(L_i)^2 \in H^{2i}(\bar{M}_{g,n}), \quad \kappa_i(i) = \frac{F_i \wedge \Delta_i \wedge \Delta_i}{2\pi} \quad (2.6)$$

It is a non-trivial property that these are stable classes, i.e., that their definition actually extends to the compactified moduli space $\bar{M}_{g,n}$. The reason is basically that the line bundles L_i remain well-defined in the stable compactification, since the points x_i will never collide. At infinity they remain at finite distance while being separated from the bulk of the surface on a ‘large’ ‘ferromagnetic’ sphere, which tends to a node.

We can now define ‘correlation functions’ by taking the wedge product of the σ_i ’s with the fundamental class of the moduli space

$$\langle \sigma_{n_1} \dots \sigma_{n_k} \rangle = \langle \sigma_{n_1}(1) \dots \sigma_{n_k}(k), \bar{M}_{g,n} \rangle \quad (2.7)$$

Of course, these intersection numbers are only non-zero if the degree of the total class equals the dimension of moduli space, which gives the ‘charge conservation’ condition

$$\sum_{i=1}^k n_i - 11 = 3g - 3. \quad (2.8)$$

Although the Chern classes $\sigma_i(L_i)$ are in principle defined in integer cohomology, their intersection numbers will be integral rational numbers, due to the orbifold nature of the moduli space.

The amazing result, first conjectured by Witten [7, 27] on the basis of the matrix model results and later proved rigorously by Kontsevich [28], states that all these intersection numbers are explicitly computable because their generating function obeys the equations of the KdV hierarchy. To state this result more precisely, it is convenient to rescale and relabel the classes σ_i as

$$O_{2n+1} = (2n+1)! \sigma_n, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (2.9)$$

After this substitution the theorem states that the string partition function

$$Z(g) = \exp \sum_{g=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \langle O_{2n+1} \rangle_g \quad (2.10)$$

is a τ -function of the KdV hierarchy. In this sense intersection theory on the (universal) moduli space is completely integrable. We note that due to the charge conservation condition (2.8), it is very easy to introduce a string coupling constant λ that keeps track of the genus g of the different surfaces that appear in the partition function (1). Indeed, if we rescale the coupling constants by

$$h_i \rightarrow \lambda^i h_i, \quad (2.11)$$

we find

$$Z(g) \rightarrow \exp \sum_{g=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \lambda^{2n+1} \langle O_{2n+1} \rangle_g \quad (2.12)$$

Before we discuss the proof of the integrability of (1), let us first discuss some weaker results related to the ‘trivial’ nature of the classes σ_i and τ_i .

2.2. THE PUNCTURE AND DILATION EQUATIONS

The only consequence of the invariance of the ‘puncture operator’ σ_n in a correlation function is that the same cohomology class is now interpreted over $\bar{M}_{g,n}$, instead of $M_{g,n}$. Since there is a natural projection map $\pi: \bar{M}_{g,n+1} \rightarrow \bar{M}_{g,n}$, where one simply forgets the position of the extra point, one might tend to conclude that the classes can be simply pulled back and that thus the correlation functions involving σ_i vanish by dimensional reasons. This is actually not true, due to subtleties at the divisor at infinity, where the forgotten point comes close to the other positions. The trick to extra operations that can be expressed through the so-called puncture equation, due to Deligne [7], which is explained in more detail in [29]

$$\langle \sigma_{n_1} \dots \sigma_{n_k} \rangle_g = \sum_{i=1, \dots, k} \langle \sigma_{n_1} \dots \sigma_{n_{i-1}} \dots \sigma_{n_k} \rangle_g \quad (2.13)$$

Figure 1.1: Mathematical formulas in scientific documents

ment of science and education. However, due to the highly academic nature of the aforementioned types of documents, their internal components have complex structures, making content extraction far from straightforward. One of the most common and important components frequently appearing in scientific documents is mathematical expressions. To perform mathematical expression extraction, in practice, two subproblems need to be solved: first, detecting regions containing mathematical expressions in images; and second, using the detected image regions to perform expression recognition. Compared to ordinary text, mathematical expressions have two characteristics that make extraction challenging:

1. Regions containing mathematical expressions often have multiple scale levels in the image, and many expressions are embedded within lines of regular text.
2. Mathematical expressions are composed of symbols with complex relationships and a large number of symbols; consequently, their textual representation is typically written in a structured language (also known as “markup language”), such as LaTeX or MathML. Figure 1.2 illustrates the process of converting a mathematical expression into LaTeX format.

Mathematical expression extraction is therefore considered a challenging problem in the field of document analysis problems. Nevertheless, mathematical expression extraction is an indispensable part of scientific document digitization, and thus solving this problem is of paramount importance. Currently, detecting and converting mathematical expressions into structured languages such as LaTeX is particularly useful in the process of writing scientific documents, significantly re-

The diagram illustrates the Mathematical Expression Recognition (MER) problem. It shows a handwritten mathematical expression $K_{\alpha}^M \frac{\partial}{\partial z_M} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi_{\alpha}}$ enclosed in a dashed box. A green arrow points downwards to another dashed box containing the corresponding LaTeX code: $K_{\alpha}^M \frac{\partial}{\partial z_M} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi_{\alpha}}$.

Figure 1.2: *The Mathematical Expression Recognition (MER) problem*

ducing writing time. Between the two subproblems of mathematical expression extraction, the recognition problem is considered more difficult, because the details in expression images are often highly complex, making it very challenging to build an automatic recognition method. In recent years, an increasing number of studies on mathematical expression recognition have been published at prestigious conferences and journals, demonstrating growing interest in this problem.

Recognizing the urgency and practical applicability of mathematical expression extraction, the topic “Building a Mathematical Expression Extraction System from Document Images” was proposed as an effort to develop a highly effective mathematical expression extraction system through researching and improving existing methods, thereby laying the groundwork for building a complete tool that enables the digitization of scientific documents to serve the academic community in Vietnam.

1.2 Objectives and Scope of the Thesis

As mentioned above, solving the mathematical expression recognition (MER) problem within an extraction system is the most challenging task and a prerequisite for building an effective extraction system. Recognizing the importance of the MER problem, in this thesis, we first focus on building a mathematical expression recognition model with high accuracy, and then combine it with expression region detection models published by other research to complete an expression extraction system. To achieve the above objectives, we carried out the following tasks:

- Survey related works on the MER problem and select an appropriate approach.

- Research and propose a model that effectively solves the MER problem.
- Research and build a large-scale database for future MER research.
- Build a complete mathematical expression extraction system using the proposed model.

1.3 Main Contributions

Through the research and development process, we summarize our main contributions in this thesis as follows:

- Proposed the Hybrid Vision Transformer model for the MER problem.
- Constructed the complete **L**arge **I**mage to **M**arkup **D**atabase (LIMD) for the MER problem.
- Completed a mathematical expression extraction system for printed text images and PDF documents.
- The source code and dataset are publicly available on GitHub¹.

¹<https://github.com/duylebkHCM/doc2tex>

Chapter 2

Theoretical Background

In this chapter, we present the theoretical foundations related to the MER problem, including basic knowledge of the TeX language, an overview of the sequence prediction problem — a general class of problems of which MER is a sub-problem — and the fundamental techniques used to solve this problem.

2.1 LaTeX Basics

2.1.1 Overview of TeX and LaTeX

TeX is a markup language created by Donald Knuth ¹ with the purpose of producing scientific documents with neat and professional formatting, such as writing thesis reports, books, or scientific papers for submission to conferences. Today, TeX is considered the standard for typesetting any type of scientific document. Unlike commonly seen word processing tools such as Microsoft Word or LibreOffice Writer for Linux, TeX uses a set of commands to define the structure of a document.

LaTeX is essentially a modified version of TeX created by Leslie Lamport ² with the purpose of simplifying TeX-based typesetting through the use of pre-built packages. However, given the diverse number of commands and characters, mastering TeX/LaTeX is not easy for beginners.

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2.1.2 Basic Mathematical Syntax in LaTeX

Mathematical expressions in LaTeX are represented through a collection of symbols, which are categorized into different groups. The purpose of this section is to reinforce basic knowledge about writing mathematical formulas in LaTeX. Some basic symbol groups are classified as follows:

- **Writing modes:** There are two basic writing modes: the *inline* mode used for writing expressions as part of a text paragraph, and the *display* mode used for writing standalone expressions. Expressions in *inline* mode are written within symbol pairs such as `\(` and `\)`, `\$` and `\$`, `\begin{math}` and `\end{math}`. For *display* mode, the symbol pairs `\[` and `\]`, `\begin{displaymath}` and `\end{displaymath}` and `\begin{equation}` and `\end{equation}` are used to contain mathematical formulas. Additionally, packages such as *amsmath* also support other writing modes like `\begin{equation*}` and `\end{equation*}`
- **Subscripts and superscripts:** Superscripts and subscripts are two commonly used notations when writing mathematical expressions in LaTeX. They are not operands or operators in expressions but are used to describe the spatial relationship between components in the expression. LaTeX uses the `_` character for subscripts and the `^` character for superscripts. An example of using these two notations in a mathematical expression is `\$a_1^2 + a_2^2 = a_3^2\$`, which produces $a_1^2 + a_2^2 = a_3^2$. Furthermore, they can also be used to represent upper and lower bounds for certain mathematical symbols such as integrals or limits.
- **Greek letters and mathematical symbols:** LaTeX supports most commonly seen mathematical symbols. Some Greek letters include `\alpha`, `\beta`, `\gamma`, binary expression operators such as `\times`, `\div`, `\oplus`, comparison operators such as `\leq`, `\neq`, and logical operators such as `\in`, `\notin`, `\subset`. Additional mathematical symbols can be found at https://www.overleaf.com/learn/latex/List_of_Greek_letters_and_math_symbols
- **Matrices:** In LaTeX, matrix representation is supported by the *amsmath* package. Some matrix environments that can be used are as follows:

Plain form	$1 \ 2 \ 3$
	$a \ b \ c$
Parenthesis form	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ a & b & c \end{pmatrix}$
Curly brace form	$\begin{Bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ a & b & c \end{Bmatrix}$

Additionally, matrices can also be written in *inline* form using the `\begin{smallmatrix}`, `\end{smallmatrix}` environment.

- **Font types:** Depending on specific mathematical symbols, different font types must be used, typically supported by packages such as *amssymb* and *amsfont*. Some commonly encountered fonts include `\mathcal`, `\mathfrak`, `\mathbb`, `\mathrm`, `\mathbf`, `\mathit`.

An important point to note when typesetting with TeX is that in TeX or LaTeX, there exist multiple tokens that represent the same character in a mathematical expression.

2.2 Sequence Prediction Problem

2.2.1 Some Representative Problems

The sequence prediction problem is a class of important problems in the field of computer science. A problem belongs to the sequence prediction class if its output data can be modeled as a sequence of tokens. This class of problems has applications spanning many fields, from computer vision and natural language processing to speech processing.

In the field of computer vision, the sequence prediction problem aims to find a model that can extract information from an input image and convert it into appropriate text form according to the specified requirements. Some subproblems within this class include Image Captioning [13], Visual Question Answering [14], Text Recognition [15], and Mathematical Expression Recognition (MER). The use of deep neural networks to solve these problems has shown outstanding results compared to other methods in recent years. Deep learning methods are primarily based on the encoder-decoder architecture, learning from data consisting of image-text pairs. The encoder extracts features from images, which are combined with textual

information through the decoder to produce the final result. Current publications on the MER problem using deep learning are fundamentally based on this general architecture. The following section will present in detail the algorithms related to this class of problems.

2.2.2 Related Theories

Convolutional Neural Network

Consider the following scenario: given a color image of size 50×50 pixels represented as a tensor³ of $50 \times 50 \times 3$. To represent all the information in this image, all pixels need to be fed into the input layer of an FC network. In this case, the input layer has 7500 nodes. Assuming the first hidden layer has 1000 nodes, the number of weights between the input layer and the first hidden layer is $7500 \times 1000 = 7,500,000$. Adding the 1000 bias variables, the total parameters needed for the first two layers is 7,501,000. It can be seen that applying an FC network to image data would consume enormous computational resources. Therefore, applying FC networks to images is infeasible.

The layers in a neural network aim to extract features from the input. However, image features are not distributed across every pixel; rather, nearby pixels tend to have stronger connections with each other. Therefore, applying convolutional layers to the neural network can solve the parameter quantity problem while still extracting features from images. Hence, convolutional neural networks are used for efficient feature extraction from images. A convolutional neural network has convolutional layers as its main component. Each convolutional layer has a size of $k \times k \times c$, where k is the height and width, c is the number of dimensions of the feature map, and s is the stride between slides. Figure 2.1 illustrates the computation process of a convolutional layer on a feature map. A convolutional neural network consists of multiple convolutional layers combined with pooling layers to reduce the size of feature maps. Additionally, each feature map may have more than one convolutional layer participating in the computation to enhance the ability to extract different types of features.

³A tensor is a matrix with more than 2 dimensions

Figure 2.1: *Computation process of a convolutional layer's output [2]*

Figure 2.2: *Structure of an RNN layer before and after unrolling [3]*

Recurrent Neural Network

Traditional neural networks have inputs and outputs that are independent of each other, meaning they are not linked in a sequence. This type of network is suitable for many problems, such as classification, where inputs are independent of each other. However, for the problem of predicting the next word in a sentence, clearly, the likelihood of a word occurring depends on many factors, including the preceding word. In such cases, a standard neural network cannot properly represent and predict correctly. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) were developed to solve such problems. This network performs the same task for all elements of a sequence, where the output depends on previous elements.

The basic structure of a recurrent neural network is as follows:

In a standard neural network, the input layer x passes through hidden layers h

Figure 2.3: Structure of an LSTM cell [3]

and produces the output layer y with full connections between layers. In contrast, in an RNN, inputs x_t are combined with the hidden layer h_{t-1} using function f_w to compute the current hidden layer h_t , from which y_t is inferred. Thus, results from previous computations are “remembered” by incorporating the hidden layer h_{t-1} to improve the accuracy of the current prediction. The computation process can be expressed as follows:

$$h_t = f_W(h_{t-1}, x_t) \quad (2.1)$$

A limitation of RNNs is the vanishing gradient problem. To address this limitation, the LSTM [16] (Long Short-Term Memory) model was developed. An LSTM cell as shown in Figure 2.3 consists of the following gates: Forget gate, Input gate, and Output gate. Equation 2.2 shows the computation steps for the hidden state value of an LSTM cell.

$$\begin{aligned} z_t &= \sigma(W_z \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t]) \\ r_t &= \sigma(W_r \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t]) \\ \tilde{h}_t &= \tanh(W \cdot [r_t * h_{t-1}, x_t]) \\ h_t &= (1 - z_t) * h_{t-1} + z_t * \tilde{h}_t \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

Sequence-to-Sequence Architecture

This is an architecture first proposed in [17] for the machine translation problem in natural language processing, and it achieved remarkable success. The success in machine translation laid the foundation for applying this architecture to

other problems, notably the MER problem, with certain modifications while fundamentally retaining the main model structure. A Seq2seq model consists of two components: the encoder and the decoder. In the original paper, the encoder is an RNN model used to encode the source sentence into a feature vector, also known as the context vector. For the image-to-text conversion problem, specifically the MER problem, the encoder is augmented with a CNN-based feature extractor before the RNN. In the decoding step, another RNN model learns to generate the target sentence for machine translation sequentially, one word at a time. The detailed procedure as shown in Figure 2.4 is as follows:

- The source sentence is passed through an embedding layer and then fed into the encoder.
- At each time step, the encoder input includes both the embedding value e of the current word $e(x_t)$ and the hidden state value from the previous time step h_{t-1} , returning the hidden state value h_t as in Equation 2.3

$$h_t = \text{EncoderRNN}(e(x_t), h_{t-1}) \quad (2.3)$$

- When the last word in the source sentence of length T words, x_T , is fed into the encoder, the final hidden state h_T is used as the context vector, representing the entire source sentence.
- The decoding process begins by inserting two special tokens $\langle \text{sos} \rangle$ and $\langle \text{eos} \rangle$ into the target sentence.
- At each time step, the decoder input is the embedding value, d , of the current word in the target sentence, i.e., $d(y_t)$, along with the hidden state value from the previous time step, s_{t-1} , where the initial hidden state s_0 equals the context vector. Thus, the decoder output is represented as in Equation 2.4

$$s_t = \text{DecoderRNN}(d(y_t), s_{t-1}) \quad (2.4)$$

- The predicted word value at each time step is obtained by passing the hidden state s_t through an FC layer to get $\hat{y}_t = f(s_t)$

Figure 2.4: *The output generation process in machine translation [4]*

Self-Attention Mechanism

The self-attention mechanism was first introduced in the paper Attention Is All You Need [5]; it is a mechanism widely used in the field of NLP. Self-attention is the core structure forming the Transformer model [5]. Given a sequence of elements, the self-attention mechanism estimates the relevance of one element to all other elements. In other words, self-attention computes weights for each element in the sequence based on the global information of the entire sequence.

Suppose we have a sequence of n elements (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) called $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$, where d is the dimensionality of the embedding vector representing each element. The goal of self-attention is to determine the relationships among all n elements by encoding them into global contextual information. To accomplish this, self-attention relies on 3 main vectors: Query (Q), Key (K), and Value (V). The Query, Key, and Value vectors function similarly to a search system like Google: when a search query is typed into the search bar (Query), the system matches the search information against a set of Keys (e.g., titles, descriptions in the database) and returns the information corresponding to matching titles (Values).

The output of self-attention is a weighted sum of value vectors, where the weight of each value is computed by a function between the key and query vectors. The Query, Key, and Value vectors are computed from the input X using 3 corresponding weight matrices $W^Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_q}$, $W^K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_k}$, $W^V \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_v}$, where $d_q = d_k$. From this,

we have $Q = XW^Q, K = XW^K, V = XW^V$ and the output as shown in Figure 2.5 is formulated as:

$$Z = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_q}}\right)V \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 2.5: Scaled Dot-Product Attention [5]

In practice, to extract different features or more complex relationships between elements in the sequence, the input data can be passed through multiple self-attention blocks simultaneously, also known as Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA). In this case, each self-attention block has its own weight matrices $W^{Q_i}, W^{K_i}, W^{V_i}$ with $i = 0 \dots (h - 1)$ where h is the number of self-attention blocks used. The outputs of each block are then concatenated into a single matrix.

Transformer Architecture

The Transformer model [5] essentially follows the encoder-decoder structure; however, unlike the RNN-based Seq2seq model, the Transformer allows parallel processing of input words in both the encoder and decoder through the multi-head self-attention mechanism presented above. The encoder of the Transformer model can consist of multiple identical encoder layers. Each encoder layer of the Transformer comprises 2 main components: MHSA and a feed-forward network, along with residual connections and normalization layers. The first encoder receives the word representation matrix added with positional information through positional encoding. Positional encoding allows encoding information about word positions be-

Figure 2.6: Multi-Head Self-Attention [5]

fore entering the encoder, because the MHSA mechanism is permutation-invariant — changing the word order does not affect the MHSA output — so positional information must be supplemented to preserve the sequential nature of the sentence. The decoder performs the function of decoding the source sentence vector into the target sentence; therefore, the decoder receives two vectors from the encoder: key and value. The decoder architecture is very similar to the encoder, except for an additional multi-head attention layer in between, used to learn the relationships between the word being translated and the words in the source sentence.

Figure 2.7: Overview of the Transformer model [5]

Chapter 3

Survey of Related Works

In this chapter, we present an overview of the research on the MER problem that we surveyed during the course of this thesis. The survey was conducted to understand the methods developed to solve the MER problem and to gain a comprehensive view of this field, thereby helping us determine the direction for selecting a specific approach and delving deeper to find improvements.

3.1 Overview of Research Directions

The MER problem has been an attractive research topic for scientists over a long period. One of the earliest studies on the MER problem dates back to the 1960s with the work of [18], which identified the need to convert images into structured languages, either in LaTeX or MathML format. The methods used at that time were primarily based on predefined rule sets derived from the syntax of mathematical expressions, also known as *syntax-directed*. Subsequent research began to expand to other methods to improve accuracy and conversion capability for more complex cases. The main approaches in the pre-deep-learning era included grammar-based approaches and tree-structure-based approaches. Methods in this period typically divided the MER problem into separate subtasks including Symbol Segmentation, Symbol Classification, and Structure Analysis. The differences among methods usually lay in how the Structure Analysis task was handled.

Tree-structure-based methods typically extract relationships between characters by constructing a tree representing the structure of the expression. In [19], a

tree was constructed by proposing a combination of top-down and bottom-up methods. Another study [20] proposed constructing a baseline tree to describe the spatial arrangement order in the two-dimensional space of mathematical expressions. The MER problem can also be modeled as a Minimum Cost Spanning Tree (MST) problem, allowing the representation of characters and spatial relationships on a graph. With this idea, a mathematical expression recognition system developed by Suzuki et al. [21] was created called InftyReader, which is considered the first commercially available MER system. The system performs recognition by representing mathematical expressions as trees and using MST for the Structure Analysis task.

Meanwhile, grammar-structure-based methods such as [22, 23, 24, 25] implemented recognition by using grammar rules and parsing rules to recognize expressions. These methods required researchers to have sufficient depth of knowledge about mathematical expression syntax and to manually define rules. In [23], the authors used the Stochastic Context-Free Grammar (SCFG) algorithm to define rule sets determining how characters are merged together.

With the development of deep learning methods in recent years, especially since the publication by [26] on the AlexNet model, which demonstrated the capability of deep learning models that prior methods could not achieve, the emergence of deep learning models has driven significant advances in many research fields, including computer vision and natural language processing. In natural language processing, the introduction of the Sequence-to-sequence (Seq2seq) architecture by [17], later improved by [27], significantly enhanced the effectiveness of Machine Translation. Since then, the Seq2seq architecture has gradually become the standard for problems in the Sequence Prediction class. Some methods using the Seq2seq architecture for other problems include [28] for Speech Recognition, [29] for the STR problem, and [30] for Image Captioning. For the MER problem, this is no exception — many methods have been proposed with the Seq2seq architecture at their core. In 2016, Deng et al. [6] published the WYGIWYS model using a Seq2seq-based architecture, proposing the use of a CNN feature extractor and an RNN-based decoder combined with the attention mechanism to predict LaTeX sequences. This is considered the first method to apply the Seq2seq architecture to the MER problem. Zhang et al. [31] proposed improvements by applying the DenseNet architecture [32] for the encoder to learn features at multiple scales. In 2019, Zhang et al. [7] proposed the *Double Attention* mechanism to better model blurred features in images. Meanwhile, [33] introduced the idea of focusing on extracting fine-grained features with

small differences due to the detailed nature of mathematical characters in images. [34] proposed using the *drop attention* method to randomly drop features during training, making the model more robust to noise. Some other methods modified the decoder architecture from RNN to one-dimensional convolutional networks to reduce model processing time, as proposed in [35]. Others proposed adding auxiliary component blocks for better data modeling, such as [36], which proposed adding a GNN block to model spatial relationships between symbols in images. The model by Pang et al. [9] addressed the need for global image information modeling as a key factor for model success and proposed the *Global Context* block for this task. Additionally, some methods focused on optimization at the full LaTeX sequence level rather than token-level optimization by applying Reinforcement Learning through *reward* functions, as proposed in [8].

It can be seen that Seq2seq-based models currently dominate the MER problem. Despite changes in components, these methods fundamentally apply the principles of the Seq2seq architecture. Therefore, we chose the Seq2seq approach for developing our model for the MER problem. In the following section, we present the operating mechanisms of several methods that we selected for in-depth study.

3.2 Research Based on the Seq2seq Architecture

Through the process of studying Seq2seq-based methods for the MER problem, we selected several methods for more detailed investigation. In this section, we present the ideas, operating mechanisms, and some results achieved by these methods, thereby laying the groundwork for our subsequent proposals.

3.2.1 What You Get Is What You See: A Visual Markup Decompiler

Proposed Method

This is considered the first paper to propose a Seq2seq-based method for the MER problem. Proposed by Deng et al. in 2016 [6], the model follows the encoder-decoder structure combined with the attention mechanism from [37] for machine translation. The combination with the attention mechanism during decoding allows the model to identify regions of interest on the feature map and thereby return the

correct character at each time step. The authors proposed a new encoding layer suitable for image input data, called the multi-row recurrence model. The overall proposed architecture has three main components:

- Convolutional network: Image features are extracted using a multi-layer feature extractor. From an image of size $H \times W$, a feature map V of size $D \times \hat{H} \times \hat{W}$ is produced, where \hat{H} and \hat{W} are the dimensions after downsampling.
- Row encoder: To ensure the feature map fed to the decoder contains ordering information, an RNN is added after the feature extractor. The goal is to help the encoder encode information from left to right and leverage horizontal contextual information to enrich the feature map. The new feature map \tilde{V} is created by running V through the RNN row by row.
- Decoder: trained as a conditional language model to output the probability of the next character based on the previous hidden state and the feature map \tilde{V} with the following formula:

$$p\left(y_{t+1} \mid y_1, \dots, y_t, \tilde{V}\right) = \text{softmax}\left(\mathbf{W}^{\text{out}} \mathbf{o}_t\right) \quad (3.1)$$

At each time step, the context vector c_t is computed based on \tilde{V} using the attention mechanism with the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_t &= a\left(\mathbf{h}_t, \left\{\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{h,w}\right\}\right) \\ \alpha_t &= \text{softmax}\left(\mathbf{e}_t\right) \\ \mathbf{c}_t &= \phi\left(\left\{\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{h,w}\right\}, \alpha_t\right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

The overall model structure is shown in Figure 3.1.

Model Evaluation

The authors also collected a new dataset to evaluate the model. The dataset contains more than 100 thousand images. Other methods along with the proposed model were trained on this dataset. The results are shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.1: Architecture of the WYGIWYS model [6].

Model	Preprocessing	BLEU (tok)	BLEU (norm)	Edit Distance	Exact Match	Exact Match (-ws)
INFTY	-	51.20	66.65	53.82	15.60	26.66
CNNENC	norm	52.53	75.01	61.17	53.53	55.72
WYGIWYS	tok	73.71	73.97	84.26	74.46	77.04
WYGIWYS	norm	58.41	87.73	87.60	77.46	79.88

Figure 3.2: Evaluation results of the model compared with other methods across metrics [6].

Remarks

The WYGIWYS model with the deep learning approach using the Seq2seq architecture with an improved encoder achieved significantly better results than other methods across all metrics. This model serves as a foundation for future improvement methods.

Figure 3.3: Architecture of the Double Attention model [7].

3.2.2 An Improved Approach Based on CNN-RNNs for Mathematical Expression Recognition

Proposed Method

Proposed by Zhang et al. [7] to improve the results published by [6]. The authors introduced a CNN-RNN-based architecture. To capture blurred features and small-sized characters, the authors proposed doubling the image size before using it for feature extraction with the CNN model. The authors used a *Double Attention* block between the encoder and decoder to more accurately locate character positions. Finally, to prevent overfitting, a Dropout layer [38] was incorporated.

Specifically, the Double Attention model consists of the following components:

- **Convolutional network:** The authors used a convolutional network with 6 convolutional layers and 5 max-pooling layers. Each convolutional layer has a kernel size of 3x3. The detailed configuration of the convolutional network is shown in Table 3.4. As mentioned, before feature extraction, the input image is doubled in size to capture blurred features from the original image.
- **Encoder:** After obtaining the feature information, these features are used for the encoder-decoder model to generate the LaTeX sequence. Here, the authors chose to use an LSTM layer as the encoder.
- **Decoder:** Using the encoder output, the decoder predicts the next character based on information from previously predicted characters and the encoder

Table 1. The Configuration of the CNN

Layer	Outputs	channels
Input (Image)	320x1000(max)	1
Convolution	320x1000	64
Max-pooling	160x500	64
Convolution	160x500	128
Max-pooling	80x250	128
Convolution	80x250	256
Max-pooling	40x250	256
Convolution	40x250	256
max-pooling	20x125	512
Convolution	20x125	512
Max-pooling	20x62	512
Convolution	20x62	512

 Figure 3.4: *Backbone configuration of the Double Attention model [7].*

Dataset	Model	Symbol Match	Edit Distance	BLEU	Image Match
IM2LAT EX-100K	Image-to-Markup	97.61	87.60	87.73	79.63
	MER	98.01	87.91	88.24	79.77
	MER-DAttn	98.4	88.57	88.42	79.81

 Figure 3.5: *Experimental results on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset [7].*

output as in Equation 3.3:

$$\begin{aligned}
 o_t &= \tanh(W_c [h_t, c_t] + b_c) \\
 p(y_{t+1} | y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_t, \bar{S}) &= \text{softmax}(W_{\text{out}} o_t)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.3}$$

Model Evaluation

The model was trained on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset. Table 3.5 shows the results of the MER-DAttn model proposed by the authors, which achieved better results compared to the method of [6]. Specifically, MER-DAttn achieved 88.42% on BLEU score and 79.81% on Image Exact Match.

Figure 3.6: *Experimental results on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset [8].*

Remarks

The proposed method leverages the CNN-RNN architecture with the *Double Attention* method to accurately determine the positions of characters in expressions. Experimental results on IM2LATEX-100K demonstrate its effectiveness compared to prior methods.

3.2.3 Translating math formula images to LaTeX sequences using deep neural networks with sequence-level training

Proposed Method

This research was conducted by Wang et al. [8] and published in the International Journal on Document Analysis and Recognition (IJ DAR) in 2021. In this work, the authors made 2 important contributions to the MER problem. First, the authors proposed a suitable model that addresses the weaknesses of previous methods, named MI2LATEX, as illustrated in Figure 3.6. Second, they proposed a new training procedure consisting of two main training stages. The additional training stage is performed at the LaTeX sequence level through an objective function implemented to optimize the entire model based on gradient derivation from reinforcement learning.

The detailed components of the model architecture are as follows:

- **Convolutional network:** Based on the VGG architecture [39], all convolutional layers have a kernel size of 3x3, with the detailed configuration shown in

Type	#maps	k	p	s
BN	–			
Convolution	512	(3,3)	(1,1)	(1,1)
MaxPooling		(2,1)	(0,0)	(2,1)
BN	–			
Convolution	512	(3,3)	(1,1)	(1,1)
MaxPooling		(1,2)	(0,0)	(1,2)
Convolution	256	(3,3)	(1,1)	(1,1)
BN	–			
Convolution	256	(3,3)	(1,1)	(1,1)
MaxPooling		(2,2)	(0,0)	(2,2)
Convolution	128	(3,3)	(1,1)	(1,1)
MaxPooling		(2,2)	(0,0)	(2,2)
Convolution	64	(3,3)	(1,1)	(1,1)
Input	Grayscale image			

#maps: the number of feature maps. *k*: kernel size. *p*: padding size. *s*: stride size. *BN*: batch normalization. The sizes are in order (height, width)

Figure 3.7: Detailed configuration of the CNN encoder [8].

Table 3.7. After feature extraction, a two-dimensional feature map is obtained instead of being flattened, to preserve spatial information.

- **Positional encoding:** To distinguish different positions in the image including left-right and top-bottom positions, the authors proposed a 2D positional encoding based on [5] as in Equation 3.4:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{PE}(x, y, 2i) &= \sin(x/10000^{4i/D}) \\
 \text{PE}(x, y, 2i + 1) &= \cos(x/10000^{4i/D}) \\
 \text{PE}(x, y, 2j + D/2) &= \sin(y/10000^{4j/D}) \\
 \text{PE}(x, y, 2j + 1 + D/2) &= \cos(y/10000^{4j/D})
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

- **Decoder:** The authors proposed using two stacked BiLSTM layers [40] to enhance the ability to model long LaTeX sequences. The attention mechanism used by the authors is similar to the traditional attention mechanism.

The authors’ second contribution is the addition of a second training stage called sequence-level training. Specifically, this training stage aims to maximize the expected reward value across the entire dataset, where the reward is a function with values from 0 to 1. Mathematically, the reward function can be expressed as follows: let $(x^{(i)}, y^{(i)})$ be the i -th training pair and \hat{y}^i be the predicted value. We

Figure 3.8: Structure of the stacked BiLSTM architecture with the attention layer [8].

define $R(y^{(i)}, \hat{y}^{(i)}) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ as the function mapping the predicted sequence value to a real number; the larger the mapped value, the higher the performance. This problem can be solved by treating it as a reinforcement learning problem as in Equation 3.5:

$$\nabla_{\theta} L_R(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{E}_{p_{\theta}(\hat{y}^{(i)} | x^{(i)})} [R(y^{(i)}, \hat{y}^{(i)}) \nabla_{\theta} \log p_{\theta}(\hat{y}^{(i)} | x^{(i)})] \quad (3.5)$$

Model Evaluation

The model was trained on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset. The authors conducted experiments under two settings: with and without reinforcement, and the results are shown in Table 3.9. It can be seen that the proposed architecture without reinforcement already achieves better results than other methods, and the addition of reinforcement further improves model effectiveness.

Remarks

Overall, the authors' proposed model has several interesting aspects, such as applying positional encoding to the VGG backbone and using two BiLSTM lay-

Model	BLEU	Image edit distance	Exact match	Exact match (-ws)	IMEGE
INFTY	66.65	53.82	15.60	26.66	–
WYGIWYS	87.73	87.60	77.46	79.88	90.26
Double attention	88.42	88.57	79.81	–	–
DenseNet	88.25	91.57	–	–	–
MI2LaTeX w/o reinforce	89.08	91.09	79.39	82.13	95.41
MI2LaTeX with reinforce	90.28	92.28	82.33	84.79	96.15

Bold values represent the highest score among all methods

Figure 3.9: *Experimental results and comparison between MI2LATEX and other methods [8].*

ers as the decoder. Experimental results show that the proposed method achieves significantly better performance than previous methods.

3.2.4 Global Context-Based Network with Transformer for Image2latex

Proposed Method

This paper by Pang et al. [9] was accepted for publication at the International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR) 2021. In this research, the authors raised the issue of how the model can maximally leverage structural and positional information in expressions. Based on this, the authors proposed a global context model with the traditional Transformer block.

The model components include:

- **Feature extractor:** The authors’ main contribution is introducing the global context block from [41] with the architecture shown in Figure 3.12, to enhance feature extraction capability. For the backbone, the authors used the ResNet architecture [11] with the configuration shown in Table 3.11.
- **Transformer-based encoder:** The authors argued that using the Transformer from [5] helps better leverage the relative positional information between characters in expressions.
- **Mask Attention:** The authors proposed using a GRU layer [37] combined with the *Mask Attention* mechanism for the decoder, as in Equation 3.6, to help the model avoid repeatedly predicting the same character multiple times. However, based on our observation, this method is not truly effective on unseen

Figure 3.10: Overall architecture of the model [9].

data, as masking information does not help the model learn useful information but only limits errors on the training dataset.

$$m_{tij} = \max(m_{ij} - a_{(t-1)ij}, 0) \quad (3.6)$$

Model Evaluation

The model evaluation results shown in Table 3.13 indicate that the model improves the BLEU score by approximately 1% compared to Zhang's method [7], and achieves an exact match accuracy of 82.13%.

Remarks

In this research, the authors proposed a global context block that enables better contextual information modeling compared to previous methods. However,

Layer	Configuration	Output			
conv1_x	$3 \times 3, 32$	96×560			
	$3 \times 3, 64$	96×560			
	<i>max_pool</i> : 2×2	48×280			
conv2_x	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 128$</td> <td rowspan="2" style="text-align: center;">$\times 1$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 128$</td> </tr> </table>	$3 \times 3, 128$	$\times 1$	$3 \times 3, 128$	48×280
	$3 \times 3, 128$	$\times 1$			
	$3 \times 3, 128$				
	GC block	48×280			
$3 \times 3, 128$	48×280				
	<i>max_pool</i> : 2×2	24×140			
conv3_x	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 256$</td> <td rowspan="2" style="text-align: center;">$\times 2$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 256$</td> </tr> </table>	$3 \times 3, 256$	$\times 2$	$3 \times 3, 256$	24×140
	$3 \times 3, 256$	$\times 2$			
	$3 \times 3, 256$				
	GC block	24×140			
$3 \times 3, 256$	24×140				
	<i>max_pool</i> : 2×2	12×70			
conv4_x	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 256$</td> <td rowspan="2" style="text-align: center;">$\times 5$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 256$</td> </tr> </table>	$3 \times 3, 256$	$\times 5$	$3 \times 3, 256$	12×70
	$3 \times 3, 256$	$\times 5$			
	$3 \times 3, 256$				
	GC block	12×70			
$3 \times 3, 256$	12×70				
	<i>max_pool</i> : 2×2	6×35			
conv5_x	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 512$</td> <td rowspan="2" style="text-align: center;">$\times 5$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>$3 \times 3, 512$</td> </tr> </table>	$3 \times 3, 512$	$\times 5$	$3 \times 3, 512$	6×35
	$3 \times 3, 512$	$\times 5$			
	$3 \times 3, 512$				
GC block	6×35				
	$3 \times 3, 512$	6×35			

Figure 3.11: *ResNet architecture used [9].*

the Transformer architecture also has the capability to perform this task, so in our observation, adding this functional block is not strictly necessary. Additionally, the use of *Mask Attention* in the decoder does not guarantee generalizability across arbitrary data cases.

3.3 Summary

Through this chapter, we presented an overview of the research history of the MER problem. During this investigation process, we also identified the main approach for our research, which is based on the Seq2seq architecture. From this, we also selected several relevant studies using the Seq2seq architecture for further

Figure 3.12: Global context block architecture used [9].

MODEL	BLEU	EDA	EMA
INFTY [1]	66.65	53.82	26.66
WYGIWYS [22]	87.73	87.60	79.88
Coarse-to-Fine Attention [23]	87.07	-	78.10
Double Attention [29]	88.42	88.57	-
our model	89.72	90.07	82.13

Figure 3.13: Comparison between different models on IM2LATEX-100K [9].

detailed survey. This serves as an important foundation for the new method proposal that we will present in detail in the following chapter.

Chapter 4

Hybrid Vision Transformer for Mathematical Expression Recognition (MER)

The methods surveyed in the previous section, despite achieving promising results, mostly still have limitations that have not been addressed, causing ineffectiveness when applied to data samples with high complexity. The design limitations of these methods include the fact that encoding spatial structure and features in images relies primarily on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) combined with Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) [40], which still have many limitations for mathematical expression data where the components have complex relationships in two-dimensional space. Additionally, the problem of over-generation or under-generation of characters in the predicted sequence has not been effectively resolved. These limitations cause current methods to fail in making predictions on complex expression images (typically with long LaTeX sequences).

With the goal of addressing the issues mentioned above, in this chapter, we present a method that we researched and proposed. The proposed method is inspired by the Vision Transformer architecture, which is widely applied in computer vision problems today. The detailed contents of this chapter include the following sections:

1. Overview of the two outstanding issues that need to be resolved, including contextual modeling in two-dimensional space and the over-parsing/under-parsing phenomenon in LaTeX sequence prediction.

2. Initial ideas for solving these issues.
3. Detailed presentation of the proposed model design and its constituent components.
4. Summary.

4.1 The Problem of Contextual Modeling in Two-Dimensional Space

Compared to ordinary text data such as handwritten text lines or text lines in administrative documents, the connections between characters within mathematical expressions are significantly more complex. This complexity is manifested in three main characteristics:

- First, the arrangement of characters in two-dimensional space, as exemplified in Figure 4.1, where expression components are distributed not only from left to right like handwritten text but also from top to bottom.
- Second, the semantic relationships between components in expressions are not explicit, leading to a much more complex inference process from images to LaTeX sequences compared to ordinary text. A typical example of non-explicitness is the superscript (\wedge) and subscript ($_$) characters that cause subsequent characters to be reduced in size. However, since they are not visible in the image, predicting their existence in the sequence becomes more difficult.
- Finally, the connections sometimes need to be established over very long distances for cases of long or multi-line expressions. Figure 4.2 shows an example of the distance between connections from one component to related components in the image.

As mentioned, previous methods have not been able to resolve these issues. In [8], Wang et al. used feature maps extracted from a VGG convolutional network [39] combined with vectors from the positional encoder to model image information. However, this approach does not address the third issue because the information from feature maps is only local — it only contains information from a certain region, also known as the receptive field [42], on the original image. Deng et al. [6], on the

other hand, used a recurrent network, specifically the LSTM model [16], to encode information along each row of the feature map. However, this approach neglects encoding information along the vertical direction. Other studies such as [43, 36] also applied similar encoding approaches as Deng et al.

Additionally, one of the popular approaches applied in text recognition problems [44, 29, 45] is using multiple Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) layers to encode contextual information in both forward and backward directions as shown in Figure 4.3. This approach allows any vector in the feature map to obtain information from vectors before and after it. However, because BiLSTM layers cannot determine the positions of input feature vectors in two-dimensional space, this approach does not achieve high effectiveness in the MER problem. Furthermore, stacking multiple BiLSTM layers causes significant computational burden and increases processing time due to the sequential design inherent in recurrent neural network models.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varphi_{1k_-} \\ \varphi_{2k_-} \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{\kappa}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} e^{ik_-x^-} e^{i\pi/2} \\ e^{-ik_-x^-} e^{-i\pi/2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

▲ MOVE to stop Mr. Gaitskell from

(a) Handwritten text image [46]

(b) Mathematical expression image [6]

Figure 4.1: Differences in spatial structure between handwritten text and mathematical expressions.

$$\alpha_p l^{D-2p} = \begin{cases} (D-2p)^{-1} \binom{n-1}{p} \\ \binom{n}{p} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{matrix} D = 2n-1 \\ D = 2n. \end{matrix}$$

Figure 4.2: Two-dimensional spatial connections between a character and other characters.

4.2 The Over-Parsing and Under-Parsing Problem

A common issue not only in the MER problem but in most sequence prediction problems that use the attention mechanism during prediction is the over-parsing and under-parsing phenomenon. This phenomenon was first mentioned by Zhaopeng et al. in [47]. In [47], the authors called this phenomenon Over-translation

Figure 4.3: Feature vectors modeled by the BiLSTM block.

$$\alpha_{p^l}^{D-2p} = \begin{cases} (D-2p)^{-1} \binom{n-1}{p}, & D = 2n-1 \\ \binom{n}{p}, & D = 2n. \end{cases}$$

Figure 4.4: The information similarity between the blue and red regions can cause the attention mechanism to make incorrect predictions, leading to characters already generated in the past being regenerated in subsequent prediction steps (over-parsing).

and Under-translation as it originated from the Machine Translation problem. In Machine Translation, this phenomenon can be understood as some words in the source sentence being translated repeatedly multiple times (over-translation) or not being translated at all (under-translation). In the context of the MER problem, this concept can be translated as some pixel regions in the image being converted to LaTeX characters (over-parsing) or being skipped during prediction (under-parsing).

This phenomenon occurs in architectures using the attention mechanism because at each prediction step, a new attention map is created; however, the model has no information about whether the attention map is attending to pixels that have already been used for prediction in the past. The lack of any control mecha-

nism makes predictions prone to errors, especially for complex data types like MER where pixel regions contain fairly similar information, causing the attention focus to shift to undesired positions, as can be seen in Figure 4.4.

4.3 Problem Formulation

Before introducing the ideas and methods we propose, we present the definition of the MER problem in mathematical form with corresponding input and output information. This information will be applied throughout the subsequent sections of this chapter.

Recalling the MER problem, this can be viewed as a type of sequence prediction problem with input data consisting of a pair of a grayscale image $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$ and a corresponding LaTeX sequence $\mathbf{Y} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_\tau\}$ that can be rendered into image \mathbf{X} , with a sequence length of τ . Each value y_i in the sequence \mathbf{Y} is a token belonging to a vocabulary of size \mathbf{K} .

The objective of this problem is to build a method capable of converting an input image into the corresponding LaTeX language, i.e., finding a mapping function $f(\mathbf{X}) = \mathbf{Y}$. In practice, we can only find a function f' that is an approximation of f . For the deep learning approach, finding the approximate function f' is performed through supervised training with the back propagation algorithm [48] on a dataset consisting of image and corresponding LaTeX sequence pairs.

4.4 Main Ideas

To address the issues raised in Sections 4.1 and 4.2, we searched for alternative solutions to current approaches. Leveraging the similarity in input and output data formats between the MER problem and the Scene Text Recognition (STR) problem [15], we based our approach on the framework widely used for the STR problem proposed by Baek et al. [49] as the main approach for building our model.

The framework for the MER problem that we constructed is shown in Figure 4.5, consisting of two main parts: the Encoder and the Decoder. The encoder includes two functional blocks responsible for extracting high-level features while downsampling the input image, and supplementing global contextual information of the entire feature map for each vector in the map. The decoder corresponds to the

Figure 4.5: General architecture of the proposed model. The model is a combination of three main components: the feature extraction block, the context modeling block, and the prediction block.

prediction block with the function of converting encoder information into a LaTeX sequence.

Regarding the issue in Section 4.1, we recognized the need for a mechanism to aggregate global information from image features — a crucial factor for modeling spatial relationships and long-range dependencies between character groups in images, since related characters are often far apart. For example, mathematical expressions typically have matching structures, where the characters ” and ” always appear together but can be far apart, or characters with mathematical correlations such as ’ f ’ and ’ dx ’.

Inspired by the success of the Transformer architecture [5] in computer vision applications [50], particularly the research by Dosovitskiy et al. at Google [51] which demonstrated the effectiveness of Transformers for image data by overcoming many weaknesses of CNN and RNN architectures, we proposed using the Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture [51] as the context modeling block of the encoder.

Compared to the typical RNN architecture, namely BiLSTM, ViT can process all input tokens simultaneously in parallel [5] instead of sequential processing, thereby improving computation time and cost. Additionally, as the input token sequence length increases, using BiLSTM becomes less effective due to the vanishing gradient problem.

Compared to the CNN architecture, ViT has several advantages:

- First, ViT uses the self-attention (SA) mechanism, which enables more efficient aggregation of information from different spatial positions compared to CNN’s sliding window design and convolution operations. Furthermore, according to research by Raghu et al. [10], ViT’s multi-head design allows each SA layer to simultaneously learn information at both short-range (local) and long-range

Figure 4.6: *Differences in receptive field expansion between ViT and the CNN model represented by ResNet50 [10]. It can be seen that for ResNet50, information is aggregated locally, while for ViT, global information aggregation is already performed at intermediate layers.*

(global) distances.

- Second, and importantly, according to [10], ViT has better capability to preserve spatial positional information of tokens compared to CNN models. Figure 4.7 shows the similarity between a token at a specific position in the feature map and its corresponding pixel region in the original image. It can be seen that ViT (rows 1 and 2) clearly shows the corresponding image region, while ResNet50 (last row) shows similarity across many unrelated image regions.

However, [10] also clearly states that although the MHSA mechanism of ViT enables the architecture to simultaneously perform attention at short-range (local) and long-range (global) distances, this requires a large amount of training data to acquire the **inductive bias** for information localization (which CNN inherently possesses). This means that with limited data, we still need the local information modeling capability from CNN architecture to ensure model performance.

From the above analyses and evaluations, we proposed that the model’s encoder will consist of a combination (Hybrid) of CNN and ViT architectures, and thus we named our proposed method **Hybrid Vision Transformer**. In this design, the CNN model is responsible for extracting high-level features from the input image into a feature vector map (the feature extraction block in Figure 4.5); the ViT model consisting of multiple stacked ViT blocks is responsible for enriching the feature map with global contextual information.

To solve the problem raised in Section 4.2, we used the method proposed in

Figure 4.7: *Differences in spatial information preservation capability between ViT and the CNN model represented by ResNet50 [10]. Rows 1, 2 show ViT’s information preservation capability; the last row corresponds to ResNet50.*

[47, 52], where the authors built a mechanism to track information about regions that have already been converted to LaTeX in the past, based on a coverage vector. Details about the construction and operation will be presented in Section 4.5.2.

In this section, we formulated the main construction ideas through research and investigation to address the previously raised issues. Additionally, we analyzed the advantages of our chosen alternative solutions compared to existing ones. In the following section, we present the detailed design of the proposed model, including the model architecture and the operation of each functional block.

4.5 Detailed Design

In this section, we present the details of the proposed model’s components, which are shown in Figure 4.8, including:

- Encoder: Feature extractor, context modeling block, 2D positional encoder.
- Decoder: Prediction block using the attention mechanism combined with coverage.

Figure 4.8: Detailed architecture of the proposed model. The mathematical expression image is passed through the encoder where the feature map is extracted by the ResNet model [11], then split into patch embedding vectors combined with positional encoding vectors as input for the context modeling block consisting of stacked ViT blocks. The output of the context modeling block includes the [CLS] embedding vector used as the initial hidden state for the decoder, and the sequence of feature embedding vectors used as **annotation** vectors for the decoder.

4.5.1 Hybrid Vision Transformer as an Encoder

Feature Extractor

As presented in Section 4.4, the feature extraction block is used to extract high-level features representing local information regions in the image, as this helps the ViT context modeling process achieve better results.

Specifically, this task is handled by a CNN model. The components of a CNN model typically include convolutional layers, max-pooling layers, and nonlinear activation functions applied to local regions of the image, and therefore they possess the **translation invariance** property. This is why each vector on the feature map represents a local region on the image, as shown in Figure 4.9.

Here, we chose a model designed based on the ResNet model [11] with some modifications to suit the MER problem. The model was proposed by [53] and applied to the STR problem. The model architecture and detailed configuration are shown

Figure 4.9: *Receptive field corresponding to each feature vector on the original image.*

in Table 4.1; the model has 32 layers, which we refer to as ResNet32.

Fundamentally, the ResNet32 model still follows the design principles of ResNet, using a total of 4 residual blocks. Some notations in Table 4.1 include:

- k: Kernel size in height and width.
- s: Stride in height and width.
- p: Padding size in height and width.
- c: Number of output channels at each layer.

The difference from the standard ResNet model is that the stride at the 3rd pooling layer and the 6th convolutional layer in Table 4.1 is changed to (1,2) instead of the usual (2,2). This is a technique commonly used in STR problems [53, 44]; however, we found it applicable to the MER problem as well. The reason is that for both problems, image data typically has information distributed more widely along the width than the height. Therefore, changing the stride to (1,2) means that at these computation layers, width reduction is not performed while only height is reduced, avoiding information compression.

Without loss of generality, suppose we have a grayscale image of size $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$. The feature extractor returns a feature map $\mathcal{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_f \times W_f \times C}$, where $H_f = \frac{H}{16} - 1$ and $W_f = \frac{W}{4} + 1$, C is the number of output channels.

Table 4.1: Architecture of the ResNet32 model.

Layer name	Configuration				Output
Input	Grayscale image				224×64
Conv2d_1	c: 32	k: 3×3	s: 1×1	p: 0×0	224×64
Conv2d_2	c: 64	k: 3×3	s: 1×1	p: 0×0	224×64
MaxPool1	k: 2×2 s: 2×2				112×32
ResBlock1	c :128, k : 3×3 c :128, k : 3×3		$\times 1$		112×32
Conv2d_3	c: 128	k: 3×3	s: 1×1	p: 0×0	112×32
MaxPool2	k: 2×2 s: 2×2				56×16
ResBlock2	c :256, k : 3×3 c :256, k : 3×3		$\times 2$		56×16
Conv2d_4	c: 256	k: 3×3	s: 1×1	p: 0×0	56×16
Pool3	k: 2×2 s: 1×2 p: 1×0				57×8
ResBlock3	c :512, k : 3×3 c :256, k : 3×3		$\times 5$		57×8
Conv2d_5	c: 512	k: 3×3	s: 1×1	p: 0×0	57×8
ResBlock4	c :512, k : 3×3 c :512, k : 3×3		$\times 3$		57×8
Conv2d_6	c: 512	k: 2×2	s: 1×2	p: 1×0	58×4
Conv2d_7	c: 512	k: 2×2	s: 1×1	p: 0×0	57×3

Context Modeling (Sequence Modeling)

To clarify the role and structure of the context modeling block, we divide it into three main parts presented sequentially:

- Self-attention mechanism for image data.
- Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture.
- 2D Position Encoding.

1. **Self-attention mechanism for image data:** This is the most important core component in the ViT architecture, enabling the model to learn long-range contextual information through mutual relationships between vectors.

To model a vector X using the self-attention mechanism, we need three matrices: query Q , key K , and value V , which are created from X through linear transformations. From these, the attention matrix E is computed as follows:

$$E = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d}} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

where d is the dimensionality of X . The softmax function maps the value E to the range $(0, 1)$, corresponding to a probability distribution. Finally, the

Figure 4.10: Main components of a unit ViT block. Unlike the original design in [5], ViT uses Layer Normalization before performing processing on the main functional blocks.

feature value O , which is the transformation of X , is computed as follows:

$$O = \text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = EV = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d}}\right)V \quad (4.2)$$

Unlike text data, to apply the self-attention mechanism to image data — or more precisely, to the feature map produced by the feature extraction block — we need to flatten the 2D matrix into a 1D vector. Additionally, performing computations on the feature map instead of the original image significantly reduces the computational load, as shown in Section 4.5.1: the feature map has a width of $\frac{1}{4}$ and a height of $\frac{1}{32}$ compared to the original image.

2. **Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture:** We apply the original design of the ViT architecture [51], where each ViT block consists of components as shown in Figure 4.10. The input to the first ViT block is the sum of patch embedding vectors and positional encoding vectors. The basic components of a ViT block include:

- Self-attention layer: used to update each element in the sequence by aggregating global information from all other elements. To ensure capturing diverse relationships between elements in the sequence at a given time, we apply Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA).
- Feed-Forward Network (FFN) block: composed of 2 Fully-Connected layers

Figure 4.11: Vision Transformer model for image classification. Only the [CLS] token embedding is used as the image representation for the classification task.

combined with the GELU (Gaussian Error Linear Unit) activation function [54], replacing the ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) [55] used in the original Transformer architecture [5]. Compared to ReLU, GELU returns values in the range $[0, 1]$ and is differentiable at 0. GELU is computed as follows:

$$GELU(x) = 0.5x \left(1 + \tanh \left[\sqrt{2/\pi} (x + 0.044715x^3) \right] \right) \quad (4.3)$$

- Layer Normalization [56] is used to stabilize the learning process of the model. Unlike the original Transformer architecture, ViT applies Layer Normalization before performing computations with the layers above.

Without loss of generality, suppose we have $\mathcal{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_f \times W_f \times C}$ as the input feature map. To convert \mathcal{F} into the appropriate input representation for ViT, i.e., a sequence of 1D embedding tokens (where “token” refers to Transformer inputs, originating from the NLP field), we apply a CNN layer with a kernel size of $p \times p$ and a corresponding stride of $p \times p$, where p is defined as the patch size. This yields a new feature map $\overline{\mathcal{F}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{H_f}{p} \times \frac{W_f}{p} \times D}$, where D is the embedding dimension. The result is then flattened into a sequence of tokens $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$, also called patch embedding vectors — these are spatial tokens, with $N = \frac{H_f \times W_f}{p^2}$ being the total number of patches.

Inspired by the BERT model [57], the ViT model is augmented with a special token $\mathbf{x}_{\text{class}}$, also called the [CLS] token, which is a learnable vector. The [CLS] token is concatenated with the other spatial tokens in the patch embedding vector \mathbf{E} as shown in Figure 4.11. During training, information is forced to propagate from spatial tokens to the [CLS] token through the multi-head self-attention mechanism. Therefore, the [CLS] embedding can be considered a global representation of image features. In practice, [CLS] was originally added to ViT for the classification task as shown in Figure 4.11. Thus, in our proposed

model as shown in Figure 4.8, we use the [CLS] embedding as the initial hidden state for the decoder instead of using the entire ViT output for this operation. ViT itself, or more precisely the self-attention mechanism, treats the input token sequence as a bag-of-words and therefore does not distinguish the order of appearance of elements in the sequence. To provide additional positional information about tokens in the sequence, we need to create a positional embedding vector \mathbf{E}_{pos} with dimension D , similar to vector \mathbf{E} . The final result is the ViT input embedding vector \mathbf{H}_0 computed by Equation 4.4.

$$\mathbf{H}_0 = [\mathbf{x}_{\text{class}}, \mathbf{E}] + \mathbf{E}_{\text{pos}} \quad (4.4)$$

where $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$, $\mathbf{E}_{\text{pos}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times D}$, the $[]$ operation concatenates the [CLS] embedding and the patch embedding vector.

In the design shown in Figure 4.8, the context modeling block consists of L ViT blocks. For simplicity, Expression 4.5 presents only the two main computation steps for a single ViT block.

In the first step, the MHSA layer processes the input embedding sequence to mix information between tokens with the global contextual information. Figure 4.12 visually illustrates a single computation head of MHSA performing the transformation of input embeddings using the attention matrix. Therefore, each token can accumulate information about other tokens in both spatial and semantic aspects throughout the model training process. This means that for MER images, MHSA enables the model to extract spatial structure for structural analysis and semantic information for character recognition.

The second step involves passing the embeddings through the FFN block. Inside the FFN block, the first Fully-Connected layer transforms the embedding from D dimensions to $4D$ dimensions, and the remaining Fully-Connected layer reduces the dimensionality back to D . The FFN block helps the embeddings perform independent information aggregation.

The computation of the MHSA layer is visualized in Figure 4.13 and can be mathematically modeled as follows. Given the input sequence from Expression 4.4 as $\mathbf{H}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times D}$, first project \mathbf{H}_0 into query matrices \mathbf{Q}^h , key matrices \mathbf{K}^h , and value matrices \mathbf{V}^h for each computation head $h \in [1, N_{\text{head}}]$ of the MHSA layer using parameter matrices $W_Q^h \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times d^q}$, $W_K^h \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times d^k}$, $W_V^h \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times d^v}$, where we set $d^q = d^k = d^v = \frac{D}{N_{\text{head}}}$ in this case. Expression 4.6 shows

Figure 4.12: *How the self-attention mechanism enhances input embeddings. The Attention Map indicates the correlation between the Key and Query matrices, which is then multiplied with the Value matrix to obtain the result.*

the concatenation of results from all computation heads, followed by projecting the resulting vector back to D dimensions using $W_O \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{head}} \cdot d^v \times D}$. The final result in Expression 4.7 contains $N+1$ elements, including N spatial embedding vectors of the image $\{h_L^1, h_L^2, \dots, h_L^N\}$ called the **annotation vectors \mathbf{A}** , and the [CLS] embedding h_L^0 .

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{H}'_\ell = \text{MHSA}(\text{LN}(\mathbf{H}_{\ell-1})) + \mathbf{H}_{\ell-1} \\ \mathbf{H}_\ell = \text{FFN}(\text{LN}(\mathbf{H}'_\ell)) + \mathbf{H}'_\ell \end{cases} \quad \ell \in [1, L] \quad (4.5)$$

$$\text{MHSA}_\ell(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = [\text{SA}_\ell^1, \text{SA}_\ell^2, \dots, \text{SA}_\ell^H] \times W_O \quad (4.6)$$

$$[h_L^0, h_L^1, h_L^2, \dots, h_L^N] = \mathbf{H}_L \quad (4.7)$$

- 2D Position Encoding:** As mentioned above, the positional embedding vector \mathbf{E}_{pos} plays an important role in integrating information about the corresponding positions of patch embedding vectors in the image. In practice, there are many ways to choose the positional encoding function for a token sequence. One can use a static sinusoidal function as in [5] or a learnable vector as in [51].

Figure 4.13: Difference in ViT usage between the classification task in Figure 4.11 and the MER task. In the MER task, all transformed embedding vectors are used as input for the decoding stage.

However, we observed that unlike natural images, mathematical expression images typically have strong semantic correlations between regions in the image — for example, the positional correlation between nested mathematical symbols or hierarchical operations that need to be accurately encoded. Based on this hypothesis, we proposed 2DPE using a 2D sinusoidal positional encoding function similar to [58]. The 2DPE function performs 1D sinusoidal positional encoding on both spatial dimensions of the input features and then concatenates them to obtain the result.

Specifically, suppose (H, W) are the height and width of the feature map, respectively, and D is the embedding dimension. The positional embedding vector of the feature map is computed by Expression 4.8:

$$2DPE(H, W, D) = [PE(h, i), PE(w, j)] \quad (4.8)$$

where $i \in [0, D/2), j \in [D/2, D)$, and $[\cdot]$ denotes the vector concatenation operator. The embedding value at each spatial dimension is computed using the following formula:

$$\begin{cases} PE(\text{pos}, t) = \sin\left(\text{pos}/10000^{t/\frac{D}{4}}\right) \\ PE(\text{pos}, t + \frac{D}{4}) = \cos\left(\text{pos}/10000^{t/\frac{D}{4}}\right) \end{cases} \quad (4.9)$$

where PE denotes 1D positional encoding, pos denotes any position along the vertical (h) or horizontal (w) direction, $t \in [0, D/4)$ when Equation 4.9 is applied to vertical positions, and $t \in [D/2, D/2 + D/4)$ for horizontal positions.

We observed that the advantage of using the sinusoidal function for positional

encoding is that using a predefined function reduces the model’s computational cost and is independent of training data — in other words, it is easy to encode positions for data with sizes larger than the training data.

4.5.2 Coverage Attention as a Decoder

A characteristic of the MER problem is that the input image size is typically not fixed, and the predicted LaTeX sequence length also varies accordingly. We chose to use an RNN architecture combined with the attention mechanism [45] as the decoder. At each time step of the decoding process, the attention mechanism computes a fixed-size intermediate vector called the context vector $\mathbf{c}_t \in \mathbb{R}^D$, based on the weighted sum between the **annotation vector** \mathbf{A} and the attention weight vector $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_t \in \mathbb{R}^N$. By using \mathbf{c}_t , the decoder can generate the appropriate LaTeX character independently of changes in input image length. We chose to use the LSTM model instead of vanilla RNN to mitigate the vanishing gradient problem.

During training, each ground-truth token y is first transformed using an embedding layer as shown in Figure 4.8 into a vector e , where highly correlated tokens (e.g., '[' and ']') have embedding values that are close to each other in the embedding space.

Figure 4.14: Difference between the standard attention mechanism and the addition of the coverage vector. Using the coverage vector as input for the attention operation increases the probability of selecting features that have not been converted in the future, and decreases the probability of features that have already been translated in the past.

At the first time step of the decoding process, we use the [CLS] token embedding as the initial state for the LSTM network. To limit the occurrence of over-parsing/under-parsing, we relied on the solution proposed in [47, 52]. The solution

proposes using an intermediate vector whose role is to trace information about attention weights generated at each past time step during decoding, or in other words, a vector that checks the degree of coverage of regions weighted in the past. Therefore, we call this vector the Coverage Vector.

The coverage vector is computed as the sum of attention weight vectors α from previous time steps, then passed through a convolutional layer to aggregate additional information between neighboring values, as detailed in Expression 4.10.

$$\begin{cases} \beta_t = \sum_{l=1}^{t-1} \alpha_l \\ \mathbf{f}_t = \text{Conv}(\beta_t) \end{cases} \quad (4.10)$$

where \mathbf{f}_t denotes the coverage vector at time step t , and we define β_0 as the zero vector at the initial time. In summary, the predicted token value $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_t \in \mathbb{R}^K$ at time step t is computed according to Equation 4.11.

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{c}_t = \text{Attention}(\mathbf{s}_{t-1}, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{f}_t) \\ \mathbf{s}_t = \text{RNN}(\mathbf{s}_{t-1}, [\mathbf{c}_t, \mathbf{e}_t]) \\ \hat{\mathbf{y}}_t = \text{Softmax}(\mathbf{s}_t) \end{cases} \quad (4.11)$$

where \mathbf{s}_j is the hidden state value at time step $j \in [0, \tau]$, *Attention* is the attention operation that takes 3 input parameters: the hidden state \mathbf{s}_{j-1} from the previous time step, the **annotation vector** \mathbf{A} , and the coverage vector. Figure 4.14 visualizes the difference compared to the standard attention mechanism. *RNN* denotes the recurrent network — in this case, we chose the LSTM layer. \mathbf{e}_t denotes the embedding vector of the ground-truth token \mathbf{y}_t during training, or the embedding vector of the predicted value \mathbf{y}_{t-1} from the previous time step during inference. *Softmax* denotes the softmax operation to generate the predicted value as a probability distribution.

4.6 Summary

In this chapter, we identified and analyzed the issues that current methods are still facing. There are two main issues: 1) Modeling contextual information in two-dimensional space such as mathematical expressions is very complex, and 2) During LaTeX sequence prediction with the attention mechanism, over-parsing/under-parsing phenomena frequently occur. Based on the identified issues and the research

process, we proposed several ideas in general form to solve these problems. The main solution we proposed is named Hybrid Vision Transformer. Additionally, we proposed the 2DPE positional encoder and applied the coverage vector to the attention mechanism. Furthermore, the detailed design of the model along with its operating mechanism was also presented. In Chapter 5, we present in more detail the implementation methodology and evaluation results compared to current SOTA methods to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed model.

Chapter 5

Experiments and Evaluation

In this chapter, we conduct experiments on standard datasets to evaluate the capability of the proposed method compared to current SOTA methods. Additionally, ablation studies are performed to investigate the contribution of each component in the proposed model. Finally, we analyze and evaluate the obtained results through visualization of attention maps in the encoder and decoder, as well as analysis of the impact of LaTeX sequence length on the model’s prediction results.

The structure of this chapter is organized as follows:

1. Dataset survey.
2. Discussion on training and prediction methods along with related algorithms and metrics.
3. Detailed experimental results on the dataset with analysis and evaluation.
4. Summary.

5.1 Dataset Survey

To ensure objectivity in model evaluation, we chose to experiment on the standard IM2LATEX-100K dataset published in 2017 by Deng et al. [6]. A brief overview of the IM2LATEX-100K dataset: the dataset was collected from approximately 60,000 papers posted on arxiv. The dataset contains a total of 103,556 mathematical expressions in LaTeX format along with corresponding images. According to the authors, the dataset has LaTeX sequence lengths ranging from 38 to 997 characters.

The construction process was performed by compiling LaTeX sequences into PDF format and then converting them to PNG images. The entire dataset is divided into three parts: a training set with 83,883 samples, a validation set with 9,319 samples, and a test set with 10,354 samples. The dataset has a total of 496 unique tokens used as the vocabulary. Similar to typical Seq2seq architectures, we added three special tokens to the existing vocabulary: the <start-of-sequence> [SOS] token, the <end-of-sequence> [EOS] token, and the [PAD] token. Therefore, the dataset has a total of 499 distinct vocabulary items.

$$G(z_1, z_2) = \begin{pmatrix} G_{++}(z_1, z_2) & G_{+-}(z_1, z_2) \\ G_{-+}(z_1, z_2) & G_{--}(z_1, z_2) \end{pmatrix} \quad v\gamma^m \partial_m \psi - \mathcal{W}^n \psi = 0.$$

$$\frac{a_\sigma}{b_\sigma} \rightarrow \begin{cases} 0, & l \leq -1, \\ \infty, & l \geq 0, \end{cases} \quad \text{at } R \rightarrow 0.$$

(A) $h_1 = f_2 = 2, h_2 = f_1 = 0 :$

(B) $h_1 = 2, f_2 = 4, h_2 = f_1 = 0 :$

(C) $h_1 = -h_2 = f_1 = f_2 = 2 :$

$N = 8, g_s = 1, C = 0 ;$

$N = 0, g_s = \frac{1}{2}, C = 0 ;$

$N = 0, g_s = 1, C = 0 .$

$$e^{M(t-t_i)} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\omega(t-t_i)) & \sin(\omega(t-t_i)) & 0 \\ -\sin(\omega(t-t_i)) & \cos(\omega(t-t_i)) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad \begin{pmatrix} J_{0,t}^a \\ J_{1,t}^a \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{D}_1^{ab} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta H_n}{\delta J_0^b} \\ \frac{\delta H_n}{\delta J_1^b} \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{D}_2^{ab} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta \tilde{H}_n}{\delta J_0^b} \\ \frac{\delta \tilde{H}_n}{\delta J_1^b} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Figure 5.1: Sample data from the IM2LATEX-100K dataset

5.2 Training and Prediction Methods

In this section, we present in detail the model training procedure and the prediction method of the proposed model.

5.2.1 Training Process

Objective Function

The objective function of the problem is based on the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) principle¹. Given a training dataset of N image-LaTeX sequence pairs x^i, y^i where $i \in [1, N]$, the training objective is to find the parameter set θ that maximizes the log-likelihood value of the dataset as in Equation 5.1.

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{MLE}} = \underset{\theta}{\operatorname{argmax}} \{L_{\text{MLE}}(\theta)\} \quad (5.1)$$

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maximum_likelihood_estimation

The value L_{MLE} is computed by averaging the logarithmic values of the probability function $p(y^i, x^i)$, which is the probability of predicting value y^i given value x^i . In the MER problem, this is a conditional probability with $p(y^i, x^i) = \sum_{t=1}^{\tau} p(y_t^i | y_1^i, \dots, y_{t-1}^i, x^i)$ where τ is the maximum length of the LaTeX sequence in the dataset, representing the sum of probabilities of predicting a character belonging to y^i at time step t .

In practice, the above procedure is equivalent to minimizing the Cross-entropy loss function L as follows:

$$L(\theta) = -\frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N p(y^i) * \log(p(\hat{y}^i)) \right) \quad (5.2)$$

. where \hat{y}^i is the model's predicted value for the i -th sample in the dataset.

Training Algorithm

In practice, when training deep learning models, the minibatch gradient descent technique [59] is commonly used, where loss computation and weight updates are performed on a subset of the dataset. Applying the minibatch gradient descent technique, we propose Algorithm 1 illustrating the model training procedure.

Algorithm 1: Step-by-step procedure for model training

Data:

- B batches of image-LaTeX sequence pairs (x^i, y^i) with $i \in [1, B]$.
- Maximum number of iterations N .

Result: Model weight set θ

```
1 for  $n$  in  $N$  do
2   for  $i$  in  $B$  do
    $y_{enc}^i = \text{Encode}(y^i)$  /* Convert tokens in  $y^i$  to integer format */
    $feature = \text{FeatureExtraction}(x^i)$  /* Model's feature extractor */
    $context\_feature = \text{SequenceModeling}(feature)$  /* Context modeling block */
    $prob = \text{Predictor}(context\_feature)$  /* Prediction block */
    $L(prob, y_{enc}^i) = \text{CrossEntropy}(prob, y_{enc}^i)$  /* Compute loss with CrossEntropy */
   Update weight set  $\theta$ 
```

5.2.2 Beam Search Algorithm

In sequence prediction problems, a common method used to select the prediction result at each time step during inference is the Greedy Search algorithm. The Greedy Search algorithm works by selecting the token with the highest probability in the vocabulary at each time step. However, this approach has a limitation: selecting the highest-probability token at a given time does not guarantee the best overall predicted sequence. In other words, local search does not guarantee an optimal global solution. The “best” factor here means that the product of conditional probabilities across all time steps must achieve the maximum value, i.e., Expression 5.3 must be maximized.

$$\prod_{t=1}^T P(y_t | y_1, \dots, y_{t-1}, \mathbf{x}) \quad (5.3)$$

The Beam Search algorithm was developed to overcome the above limitation of the Greedy Search algorithm. The Beam Search algorithm operates as follows:

1. Initialize the **beam width** as K , the number of hypotheses or predicted sequences considered at each time step.
2. At each time step, generate K new hypotheses for each hypothesis in the active hypothesis set.
3. Compute the probability value for each hypothesis.
4. Select the K hypotheses with the highest values.
5. Discard the remaining hypotheses.

Therefore, the Beam Search algorithm increases the chance of finding the optimal solution compared to Greedy Search.

5.2.3 Inference Process

After the training process is completed, we use the model with trained weights for prediction. Algorithm 2 describes the steps needed to obtain predictions from images. During inference, to enhance prediction accuracy, we use the Beam Search algorithm instead of Greedy Search.

Algorithm 2: Step-by-step procedure for the inference process

Data:

- Grayscale image X .
- Beam width K .

Result: Predicted LaTeX sequence Y_{str}

```
feature = FeatureExtraction( $X$ ) ; /* Model's feature extractor */  
context_feature = SequenceModeling(feature) ; /* Context modeling  
block */  
prob = Predictor(context_feature,  $K$ ) ; /* Prediction block */  
 $Y$  = argmax(prob)  
 $Y_{str}$  = Decode( $Y$ ) ; /* Convert numerical values back to  
corresponding tokens */
```

5.2.4 Image Augmentation

Image augmentation is an important step in the model training process, helping the model become more robust on data samples not used for training, as well as mitigating overfitting. A model robust to noise factors is also an important condition for using the model in practical systems. For the MER problem, we used the following image augmentation techniques during model training:

1. Random Moving: randomly shifting the expression region in the image.
2. Random Rotation: randomly rotating the expression region in the image.
3. Random Brightness: randomly changing the image brightness.
4. Random Sharpness: randomly changing the image sharpness.

For random moving, we implemented this by using image processing operations to obtain the bounding rectangle around the mathematical expression, then using the top-left corner coordinate of the rectangle as a reference point and changing its value to shift the image, as illustrated in Figure 5.2. Figure 5.3 visualizes some data samples after being transformed using combinations of the above augmentation techniques.

5.2.5 Input Data Processing

Image data in the IM2LATEX-100K dataset is divided into multiple size groups with height and width divisible by 32. This is a data processing technique specific to

Figure 5.2: Illustration of the Random Moving augmentation technique.

$$\langle \mathcal{O}[\vec{\xi}] \rangle_{\xi} = \frac{\int_{\xi(0)=\xi(1)} \mathcal{D}\vec{\xi} e^{-S} \mathcal{O}[\vec{\xi}]}{\int_{\xi(0)=\xi(1)} \mathcal{D}\vec{\xi} e^{-S}}$$

(a) Random (move+rotate+sharpness)

$$\vec{\phi} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ 0 \\ \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix},$$

(c) Random (move+brightness)

$$r_- = \frac{(4M)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{s} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{s^2 - Q^2} \left(\frac{2}{M}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - s}}{2\alpha}$$

(b) Random (move+rotate+brightness)

$$K_{ab}^- = \frac{\epsilon}{4} (E_{aa} - E_{bb} + E_{\theta(a)\theta(a)} - E_{\theta(b)\theta(b)}),$$

$$M_{ab}^- = \frac{\epsilon}{4} (E_{aa} - E_{bb} - E_{\theta(a)\theta(a)} + E_{\theta(b)\theta(b)}),$$

(c) Random (move+rotate+brightness)

Figure 5.3: Illustration of augmentation results on IM2LATEX-100K data.

the MER problem, where during training, images of the same size can be grouped into the same training batch. As mentioned earlier, the MER training process follows the minibatch gradient descent principle, where images in the same batch must have equal sizes. However, unlike natural images where sizes can be freely adjusted, for the MER problem, such resizing would significantly affect training results because small details in images could be stretched or compressed too much, substantially degrading data quality.

The solution is to preprocess image data by padding the height and width so that image dimensions share a common divisor, which we chose as 32. Images can then be grouped into clusters of the same size. During training, we simply randomly select data samples from the same group as the training batch. The entire process is illustrated in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: *Input data processing pipeline before model training.*

5.2.6 Evaluation Metrics

Before diving into experimental details, we present the evaluation metrics commonly used for the MER problem. For the MER problem, current studies typically use two main metric systems: text-based metrics and image-based metrics. The need for evaluation on both metric systems arises because:

1. Since the model is trained to generate text sequences, text-based metrics are necessary to verify the stability and effectiveness of the model.
2. Nevertheless, since the IM2LATEX-100K dataset is not yet thoroughly standardized, cases where different tokens represent the same symbol are inevitable. Therefore, evaluating solely based on text metrics may not be objective in comparing methods. Thus, image-based metrics are supplemented to ensure objectivity in the evaluation process.

Text-Based Metrics

1. **BLEU score:** BLEU (BiLingual Evaluation Understudy) was proposed by [60] and is a popular metric commonly used in Machine Translation problems [17, 37]. The BLEU score is a number between 0 and 1 indicating the similarity between the model-generated text and a set of reference texts. The similarity

in purpose allows the BLEU score to be used as a metric for the MER problem. The mathematical representation of BLEU score is as follows:

$$\text{BLEU} = \underbrace{\min \left(1, \exp \left(1 - \frac{\text{reference-length}}{\text{output-length}} \right) \right)}_{\text{brevity penalty}} \underbrace{\left(\prod_{i=1}^4 \text{precision}_i \right)^{1/4}}_{\text{n-gram overlap}} \quad (5.4)$$

where precision is computed as follows:

$$\text{precision}_i = \frac{\sum_{\text{snt} \in \text{Cand-Corpus}} \sum_{i \in \text{snt}} \min(m_{\text{cand}}^i, m_{\text{ref}}^i)}{w_t^i = \sum_{\text{snt}' \in \text{Cand-Corpus}} \sum_{i' \in \text{snt}'} m_{\text{cand}}^{i'}} \quad (5.5)$$

Some notable symbols:

- (a) m_{cand}^i : the number of i-grams in the predicted sentence that match the reference sentence.
- (b) m_{ref}^i : the number of i-grams in the reference sentence.
- (c) w_t^i : the total number of i-grams in the predicted sentence.

Equation 5.5 shows two main components:

- (a) Brevity penalty: a coefficient used to penalize predicted sentences that are too short compared to the reference sentence.
- (b) n-gram overlap: counts the total number of matching 1-grams, 2-grams, 3-grams, and 4-grams between the predicted and reference sentences.

In most research, the value of N used is 4, also known as BLEU-4.

2. **Edit distance (TED):** The edit distance metric, also known as Levenshtein distance, is a metric that determines the difference between two sequences. It indicates the minimum number of tokens that need to be edited (added, deleted, or replaced) to transform the predicted sentence into the reference (ground-truth). From this, the edit distance is computed as follows:

$$\text{TED} = 1 - \frac{S_c + D_c + I_c}{N_c} \quad (5.6)$$

where:

- S_c : Number of tokens replaced.
- D_c : Number of tokens deleted.

- I_c : Number of tokens inserted.
 - N_c : Total number of tokens in the reference sentence.
3. **Accuracy (Acc)**: Accuracy simply calculates the total number of correctly predicted sentences over the total number of evaluated samples. This metric is used for evaluation at the full sequence level.

Image-Based Metrics

1. **Image Edit Distance (IED)**: To use this metric, the first step is to render images from the predicted LaTeX sequences. The rendering method will be introduced in Section 6.2.4 of the next chapter.

The idea behind IED comes from treating pixels in images similarly to characters in text sequences, thereby applying the edit distance computation to evaluate the difference between the reference image and the rendered image.

The input image is first converted to binary form and then flattened into a 1D vector, where each element is a sequence of 0 and 1 values.

2. **Exact Match Rate Accuracy (EMA)**: The EMA metric is computed based on comparing the reference image and the rendered image. The result is the ratio of completely identical image pairs to the total number of reference images. Here, we use this metric on images with excess white space removed, also known as EMA(w/o space).

5.3 Experiments on the IM2LATEX-100K Dataset

With the information provided in previous sections, we now present the detailed experiments conducted. The results compared to current SOTA methods, as well as some analyses of the model's predictions, are organized as follows:

1. Experimental configuration.
2. Quantitative results.
3. Qualitative results.
4. Ablation study.
5. Analysis and evaluation.

5.3.1 Experimental Configuration

Model:

For the encoder, we set the number of output channels for the ResNet32 model to $C = 512$. Unlike the original ViT design in [51], we reduced the number of MHSA heads to $N_{head} = 8$ and used only $L = 6$ ViT blocks for feature map modeling. The patch embedding dimension is $D = 256$, and the patch size is set to 2. Finally, we set the hidden dimension of the FFN layers to $d_{ffn} = 1024$.

For the decoder, we used a kernel size of 5×5 and 128 output channels for the Conv layer mentioned in Section 4.5.2. Both the LSTM hidden state dimension and the input token embedding size are set to $d_{emb} = 256$. Additionally, to mitigate overfitting, we used a Dropout layer [38].

Training and inference process:

During training, at each decoder time step, the decoder receives the embedding value of the corresponding ground-truth token instead of using the predicted value from the previous time step, also known as the **Teacher Forcing** method². Additionally, we set the maximum length for all LaTeX sequences to 150. During inference, we use the Beam Search algorithm with a **beam width** of 5 to avoid local optima in predictions.

The entire model was trained from scratch (without any pretrained weights) for a total of 300,000 iterations with a batch size of 32. The model was trained with the AdamW optimizer [61] with an initial learning rate of 5×10^{-4} and a learning rate decay of 2×10^{-6} . After each iteration, the learning rate was adjusted based on the warm-up cosine schedule, similar to the approach in [5]. Additionally, image augmentation methods were also applied as mentioned.

Experimental Tools

- **Hardware information:**
- **Language and Framework:**

– Language: Python 3.8.5

²<https://machinelearningmastery.com/teacher-forcing-for-recurrent-neural-networks/>

No.	Configuration
1	NVIDIA V100 RAM 32GB
2	NVIDIA A100 RAM 40GB

Table 5.1: *Hardware information***Table 5.2:** *Comparison of results between methods on the IM2LATEX-100K test set*

Method	Acc	BLEU-4	EDA	EMA (w/o space)
Global Context [9]	-	89.72	90.07	82.13
Double Attention [7]	-	89.4	90.9	84.1
MI2LATEX w/o reinforce [8]	-	89.08	91.09	82.13
Ours	48.39	89.94	92.23	86.48

* We only evaluated the MI2LATEX version without Reinforcement Learning

– Framework: PyTorch 1.8.1

5.3.2 Quantitative Results

We compared the proposed model with other methods on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset to confirm the effectiveness of our design. The results in Table 5.2 show that our method achieves better results than [9], thereby demonstrating the effectiveness of using the ViT architecture compared to the global context block from [9]. Additionally, for image-based metrics such as EMA, our method shows an improvement of approximately 2.4% compared to [7]. However, the results in Table 5.2 also reveal that the Acc metric is quite low compared to other metrics such as EMA at 86.48%, indicating that for the MER problem, evaluation based on the Acc metric is not truly objective.

5.3.3 Qualitative Results

Some prediction results of the proposed model on the test set.

For the samples in Figure 5.5, it can be seen that despite visual similarity, the text content is not entirely identical, as reflected in metrics such as BLEU score or TED. The reason is that some mathematical symbols are represented by more than one type of token in LaTeX. In the IM2LATEX-100K dataset, many such cases have

not been processed, so the model trained on this data does not guarantee consistent prediction results.

For Figure 5.6, these are cases where the rendered image has a different structure from the ground-truth image. In the first case, the model has not predicted the spatial structure well; the reason we identified is that this is a multi-line expression image, while in practice, the IM2LATEX-100K dataset has only about 5,000 multi-line samples out of over 80,000, leading to the model not learning well on this data type. In the second case, the predicted structure is nearly correct with only minor differences in the number of whitespace characters.

$$\chi = \frac{C_F g^2}{8\pi} \left(1 - \frac{g^2}{8\pi^2} \left[\frac{11C_A - 2n_f}{3} \left(\frac{1}{n-4} + \ln \frac{m^2}{4\pi\nu^2} \right) + \Phi + O(g_0^2; n-4) \right] \right), \quad \chi = \frac{C_F g^2}{8\pi} \left(1 - \frac{g^2}{8\pi^2} \left[\frac{11C_A - 2n_f}{3} \left(\frac{1}{n-4} + \ln \frac{m^2}{4\pi\nu^2} \right) + \Phi + O(g_0^2; n-4) \right] \right),$$

(a) Left: Ground truth, Right: Rendered image-BLEU:86.98-TED:94.95

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) := ip_0 \nabla_{\mathbf{p}} - \frac{\mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{p}}{p_0 + m}, \quad \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) := -i\mathbf{p} \times \nabla_{\mathbf{p}} + \mathbf{s} := \mathbf{L}(\mathbf{p}) + \mathbf{s}, \quad \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) := ip_0 \nabla_{\mathbf{p}} - \frac{\mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{p}}{p_0 + m}, \quad \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) := -i\mathbf{p} \times \nabla_{\mathbf{p}} + \mathbf{s} := \mathbf{L}(\mathbf{p}) + \mathbf{s},$$

(b) Left: Ground truth, Right: Rendered image, BLEU:92.13-TED:96.39

Figure 5.5: Data samples with matching ground truth and rendered images.

$$\begin{aligned} C_r^{(I)} &= C_{-r}^{(I)} = \frac{k}{2} \sqrt{-\tau_0} J_\nu(-r\tau_0) & D_r^{(I)} &= D_{-r}^{(I)} \\ D_r^{(I)} &= D_{-r}^{(I)} = \frac{k}{2} \sqrt{-\tau_0} J_{-\nu}(-r\tau_0) & &= \frac{k}{2} \sqrt{-\tau_0} J_{-\nu}(-r\tau_0) \\ C_n^{(I)} &= D_n^{(I)} = 0 \text{ for } n \neq \pm r & &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

(a) Left: Ground truth, Right: Rendered image-BLEU:17.49-TED:36.86

$$C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(N)} = \begin{cases} (K_{\alpha\gamma})^{N-1} K_{\beta\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta} \epsilon_{\gamma\delta} & ; N \in \text{even} , \\ (K_{\alpha\gamma})^N \delta_{\alpha\delta} \delta_{\gamma\beta} & ; N \in \text{odd} . \end{cases} \quad C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(N)} = \begin{cases} (K_{\alpha\gamma})^{N-1} K_{\beta\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta} \epsilon_{\gamma\delta} & ; N \in \text{even} , \\ (K_{\alpha\gamma})^N \delta_{\alpha\delta} \delta_{\gamma\beta} & ; N \in \text{odd} . \end{cases}$$

(b) Left: Ground truth, Right: Rendered image-BLEU:88.87-TED:93.33

Figure 5.6: Data samples with differing ground truth and rendered images.

5.3.4 Ablation Study

In this section, we conduct additional experiments to better understand the model's operating mechanism.

Role of Model Components

To better understand the effectiveness of each component in the proposed model, we compared prediction results between a baseline model and different versions of the proposed model. These versions were created by sequentially replacing or adding components of the baseline model with blocks from the proposed model.

For the baseline model, we chose the VGG architecture [39] as the feature extractor, used no context modeling block, and employed the standard attention mechanism as the predictor, similar to [45]. For the feature extractor, we compared between the VGG architecture and our proposed ResNet32. For the context modeling block, we compared between BiLSTM from [45], and we also experimented with the case where the ViT input is a 1D feature map obtained by averaging along the height of the feature map, which we call ViT-1D, to distinguish from our proposed ViT-2D version. Finally, we also compared three versions of the prediction block: the standard attention version, our proposed coverage attention version, and a Transformer Decoder from [5]. Details of the experimental settings and corresponding results are shown in Tables 5.3 and 5.4.

Table 5.3: Detailed configurations of the ablation experiments, where ‘None’ indicates that no functional block was used at that position.

Experiment	Encoder		Pred.
	Feat.	Context.	
Baseline	VGG	None	Attn
V1	ResNet	None	Attn
V2	VGG	ViT-1D	Attn
V3	VGG	BiLSTM	Attn
V4	VGG	ViT-2D	Attn
V5	VGG	None	Transformer Decoder
V6	VGG	None	Coverage-Attn
V7	ResNet	ViT-2D	Coverage-Attn

The results from Table 5.4 show that using the ResNet32 model instead of VGG significantly improves the baseline across all metrics, with Acc increasing by approximately 15%. This suggests that the ResNet32 model, originally used for STR, is a suitable choice for the MER problem. For the context modeling component, we observed that adding the ViT-2D block to the baseline yields the best results. It demonstrates better long-range relationship modeling compared to BiLSTM and better two-dimensional spatial structure preservation compared to ViT-1D. Finally, the coverage attention mechanism proves to be a suitable choice for the prediction block due to its ability to trace past attention weight information.

Impact of Positional Encoding

To further investigate the role of our 2D positional encoding (2DPE), we compared prediction results on the IM2LATEX-100K test set between the model using

Table 5.4: Ablation study results evaluating the functional blocks of the proposed model. *Feat.* denotes the feature extraction block, *Context.* denotes the context modeling block, *Pred.* denotes the prediction block. Results are evaluated on the IM2LATEX-100K validation set.

Component	Experiment	Acc %	BLEU-4 %	TED %	params $\times 10^6$
Feat.	Baseline	22.15	79.12	77.32	7.05
	V1	37.55	85.90	89.90	45.76
Context.	Baseline	22.15	79.12	77.32	7.05
	V2	34.97	87.73	92.23	12.13
	V3	43.69	90.61	94.52	9.75
	V4	44.42	91.48	94.88	12.19
Pred.	Baseline	22.15	79.12	77.32	7.05
	V5	42.06	90.12	93.04	15.52
	V6	42.58	90.23	93.12	7.09
	Overall V7	49.30	92.33	95.60	50.95

2DPE and the model using only the positional encoding from [5]. The results in Table 5.5 show that using 2DPE yields better results across all metrics. Notably, the EMA metric improved by approximately 4%.

Table 5.5: Comparison between two positional encoding methods.

Positional Encoding	Acc	BLEU-4	IED	EMA (w/o space)
1D	45.78	88.84	89.31	82.93
2D	48.39	89.94	92.23	86.48

Impact of Initialization Vector

To further investigate the benefit of using the [CLS] token embedding as the initial value for the decoder hidden state, we compared results between two versions of the proposed model: one without using the [CLS] token and one using it as the initial value as described. Table 5.6 shows the results on the IM2LATEX-100K test set. The results demonstrate that the information provided by the [CLS] token significantly improves prediction results.

Table 5.6: Comparison of two hidden state initialization settings on the proposed model

Use init	Acc	BLEU-4	IED	EMA (w/o space)
✓	48.39	89.94	92.23	86.48
✗	43.87	81.73	89.36	81.02

Impact of Image Augmentation

To evaluate the impact of image augmentation during training, we compared prediction results between the model trained with augmented images and the model trained only on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset. The results in Table 5.7 demonstrate the benefits of using image augmentation techniques.

Table 5.7: Comparison of prediction results between the model with and without image augmentation.

Image augmentation	Acc	BLEU-4	IED	EMA (w/o space)
✓	48.39	89.94	92.23	86.48
✗	45.68	84.53	89.58	83.67

5.3.5 Analysis and Evaluation

The analysis and evaluation section provides further clarification of the prediction results from the proposed model, as well as visualizing how the model interacts with data to produce results.

Impact of LaTeX Sequence Length

Given a list of LaTeX sequences to evaluate, we grouped sequences with token length differences not exceeding 15 units into the same group, resulting in length groups such as [0, 15], [15, 30], [30, 45], and so on. For sequences with lengths exceeding 150, they were placed in the same group. The purpose of this grouping is to evaluate the model’s stability when predicting across different length groups.

We compared the average EMA (w/o space) values within each length group between the proposed model and the baseline model. Figure 5.7 shows that the proposed method maintains better stability against LaTeX sequence length variations compared to the baseline model. For images with LaTeX sequences longer than 100 tokens, the model still achieves EMA accuracy above 70%, and even for cases where the token length exceeds 150 — while the maximum training data length is 150 tokens — the model still achieves up to 26% accuracy.

Figure 5.7: Comparison between the proposed model and the baseline model at specific length groups.

Encoder Attention Map Visualization

To better understand the encoder’s operation, we visualized the self-attention map of the [CLS] token over the other spatial embedding vectors. To extract the ViT self-attention map, we relied on the method published in [62]. Figure 5.8 shows the information regions attended to by the [CLS] token, thereby confirming the global information modeling capability of the ViT architecture and its suitability for context modeling in the MER problem.

Figure 5.8: Illustration of the [CLS] token embedding’s self-attention map.

Decoder Attention Map Visualization

Additionally, we visualized the LaTeX sequence decoding process of the decoder. The decoding process for an image is illustrated in Figure 5.9. It can be seen that at each decoding step, the decoder focuses only on image regions related to

the character being generated, and no over-parsing or under-parsing phenomenon occurs. Furthermore, we can also see that the coverage attention mechanism works well in two-dimensional space.

Figure 5.9: *Illustration of step-by-step LaTeX token generation.*

5.4 Summary

The main purpose of this chapter is to confirm the effectiveness of the proposed model compared to other methods. To achieve this goal, we implemented related content including introducing the experimental dataset, outlining the training and prediction methods, describing the data processing approach, and introducing the evaluation metrics in detail. Beyond comparing results with SOTA models, the more important aspect was understanding the operation and role of each component in the model. Therefore, we conducted a series of supplementary experiments to evaluate the contributions of our proposals and to better understand how the model makes predictions.

Chapter 6

The Large Image to Markup Database (LIMD)

6.1 The Data Scarcity Problem for the MER Task

Current deep-learning-based MER research such as [33, 35, 36, 63, 64] mostly conduct experiments and evaluations on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset published by Deng et al. [6] six years ago. This is considered the largest publicly available dataset for the MER problem. In practice, there exist some other datasets used for this problem such as [21]; however, these datasets are small in size and not very diverse, and were primarily used for traditional non-deep-learning methods. The data was collected by the authors from scientific papers posted on the arXiv¹ website. After processing and filtering, the authors obtained the final dataset with 103,556 mathematical expressions. Currently, the IM2LATEX-100K dataset is accepted as a benchmark dataset used for comparing the effectiveness of different methods.

Despite its superiority in size and diversity of sample distribution compared to previous datasets, IM2LATEX-100K also has several limitations, including:

1. The dataset size no longer meets the demands of current deep learning models, especially methods using architectures that require large amounts of data such as Transformer [5], thereby limiting research on new methods.
2. With 100,000 samples, the dataset is insufficient for training models applicable

¹<https://arxiv.org/>

Transform	Original	Normalized
SubSup	H^I_1	H_I^1
ReqBrack	H^I	$H^{\{I\}}$
Desugar	H'	$H^{\{\prime\}}$
ExpOperators	\sin	sin
InfixPrefix	\over	$\frac{\{\}\{\}}$
MatrixEnv	\matrix	$\begin{array}\dots$
Drop	$\label{\}$	-

Figure 6.1: *Types of LaTeX tokens normalized in IM2LATEX-100K [6]*

in practice due to inadequate diversity.

3. Although the authors performed some data normalization tasks to reduce ambiguity between expression components that share the same visual representation as shown in Figure 6.1, through our survey of the dataset, we found that quite many ambiguous characters remain, potentially affecting the model’s learning capability.

Given these limitations, we recognized that building a new database to replace IM2LATEX-100K is a necessary task. Therefore, in this chapter, we present the process of constructing a new dataset for the MER problem. We named the dataset **Large Image to Markup Database**, or **LIMD** for short. The dataset we constructed focuses on three key factors: **Consistency**, **Diversity**, and **Complexity**.

6.2 Database Construction Process

Based on the construction of the IM2LATEX-100K dataset as described by the authors in [6], we proposed a general pipeline for building an MER dataset consisting of 6 main steps as shown in Figure 6.2, following the arrow direction as follows:

1. **Step 1:** Collect raw data consisting of documents with LaTeX source code containing mathematical expressions from the internet.
2. **Step 2:** Filter data samples that satisfy predefined constraints.
3. **Step 3:** Normalize the raw dataset.
4. **Step 4:** Render images from the normalized LaTeX data.

Figure 6.2: *LIMD database construction pipeline. Consisting of 6 main steps.*

5. **Step 5:** Perform post-processing steps.
6. **Step 6:** Analyze and remove outlier images from the dataset to obtain the final dataset.

Below, we present in detail the execution and results obtained at each step.

6.2.1 LaTeX Data Collection

The first task is to select the raw data source. To ensure data diversity, we chose to collect data from scientific papers posted on the arxiv² website. Papers on arxiv are divided into different research fields. We chose to collect LaTeX data from the fields listed in Table 6.1, with each field having a separate URL.

Table 6.1: *Data source information*

Field name	Abbreviation	URL
Computer Science	cs	https://arxiv.org/archive/cs/
Mathematics	math	https://arxiv.org/archive/math/
Statistics	stat	https://arxiv.org/archive/stat/
Physics	physics	https://arxiv.org/archive/physics/
High Energy Physics	hep-th	https://arxiv.org/archive/hep-th/
Nonlinear Sciences	nlin	https://arxiv.org/archive/nlin/
Quantum Physics	quant-ph	https://arxiv.org/archive/quant-ph/

We used the Python³ language combined with the BeautifulSoup⁴ library to perform data collection. Figure 6.3 shows the structure of a URL to a paper on

²<https://arxiv.org/>

³<https://www.python.org/downloads/>

⁴<https://www.crummy.com/software/BeautifulSoup/>

[https://arxiv.org/list/\[FIELD_NAME\]/\[YEAR\]\[MONTH\]/\[PAPER_ID\]](https://arxiv.org/list/[FIELD_NAME]/[YEAR][MONTH]/[PAPER_ID])

Figure 6.3: *URL structure of a paper on arxiv. Where FIELD_NAME includes the abbreviations in Table 6.1, YEAR includes the last two digits of the years, MONTH is the list of months, and PAPER_ID is the ID corresponding to each paper.*

arxiv. With this structure, we performed the following algorithmic steps to access any paper:

1. **Step 1:** Randomly select a *FIELD_NAME* value from the predefined set.
2. **Step 2:** Randomly select a *YEAR* value from the set corresponding to the *FIELD_NAME* value.
3. **Step 3:** Randomly select a *MONTH* value from the set corresponding to the choices in Steps 1 and 2.
4. **Step 4:** Randomly select a *PAPER_ID* corresponding to Steps 1, 2, and 3.
5. **Step 5:** End one iteration, return to Step 1.

The process stops when a predetermined number of iterations is reached. At the end of the data collection process, we obtained a volume of raw data consisting of papers shown in Table 6.2.

Table 6.2: *Number of collected papers by research field*

Field name	Number of papers
Computer Science	46280
Mathematics	6320
Statistics	8320
Physics	24680
High Energy Physics	15960
Nonlinear Sciences	23400
Quantum Physics	8560
Total	133520

6.2.2 Data Filtering

After the data collection step was completed, we began the process of extracting mathematical expressions (if any) from each paper and filtering to remove data that did not meet requirements.

To extract mathematical expressions from papers, we relied on LaTeX-designated tokens such as:

- `$....$`
- `$$...$$`
- `\begin{equation}... \end{equation}`
- `\begin{displaymath}... \end{displaymath}`

During the filtering process, we considered the following main criteria/targets:

- Case 1: Minimum and maximum length of the LaTeX sequence.
- Case 2: Minimum number of tokens in the sequence.
- Case 3: Token types that define spacing or spacing alignment.
- Case 4: Token types related to graphics or color representation.
- Case 5: Other token types that have no role in the expression.

Below, we analyze in detail the handling approach for each case.

- * Case 1: We chose to keep only LaTeX sequences with a minimum of 30 characters⁵ and a maximum of 1,000 characters. The reason is to avoid cases where expressions have only one or two characters or situations where multiple expressions are captured simultaneously.
- * Case 2: We chose to keep only LaTeX sequences with a minimum of 6 tokens. The reason is to avoid extracting expressions that are meaningless but could still exist, for example, the expression `\begin{array} [r] \end{array}` has a total of 5 tokens but cannot be rendered into an image.
- * Case 3: In LaTeX, there are many token types that support alignment or spacing functions. Some examples include `\raisebox`, `\boxed`, `\vcenter`, `\allowbreak`, and tokens like `\hspace` and `\vspace` that require exact spacing information. From the perspective of converting an expression image to LaTeX, it is very difficult to determine spacing information precisely by visual inspection alone. Therefore, these tokens can be removed from the LaTeX sequences as they are not necessary in the training vocabulary.

⁵Note that characters here differ from tokens, which refer to the smallest meaningful units in the LaTeX vocabulary.

- * Case 4: Similar to Case 3, some tokens support graphics-related tasks or color representation such as `\begin{picture}`, `\begin{fmfgraph}`, `\color`, `\textcolor`. LaTeX sequences containing these tokens are skipped.
- * Case 5: Sometimes in mathematical expressions, authors add auxiliary tokens for specific purposes. For example, the `\nonumber` token is used when the author does not want the expression in the `\begin{equation}`, `\end{equation}` environment to be numbered. Some other tokens include `\notag`, `\ref`, `\cite`. Removing these tokens does not affect the overall structure of the expression.

At the end of the expression extraction and filtering process from the raw paper data, the number of LaTeX sequences we obtained was 1,622,837 expressions from 133,520 papers.

6.2.3 Data Normalization

The next step in the dataset construction process as shown in Figure 6.2 is data normalization. This is considered the most important step to ensure a consistent dataset — one of the prerequisites for developing new methods. However, the data normalization process is time-consuming. To achieve this goal, we relied on two main strategies. First, through observation of data from the IM2LATEX-100K dataset to find cases that have not been normalized. Second, through a well-organized dictionary available online; here, we found that the dictionary provided by the KaTeX⁶ library, a library supporting LaTeX-to-image compilation in web browsers, is a relatively comprehensive dictionary supporting most tokens necessary for mathematical expressions.

Based on these two strategies, we made the following observations about the data:

1. **Observation 1:** In the IM2LATEX dataset expressions, there exist many redundant pairs of braces ” and ”. For example, some expressions in the dataset are written as: `{ } { { x + y } } = 2`. The existence of many redundant brace pairs inadvertently creates noise in the data, making model training more difficult.
2. **Observation 2:** Besides redundant brace pairs, there also exist many cases of redundant `\begin{array}`...`\end{array}` environments. Many expressions,

⁶<https://katex.org/docs/supported.html>

despite having only a single line and no matrix structure, still contain this environment pair in the LaTeX sequence. This noise factor is particularly more dangerous than the previous case because the model, if not well designed, could make incorrect predictions.

3. **Observation 3:** Multiple types of whitespace tokens exist, each with different whitespace widths. Some whitespace-creating tokens according to the KaTeX dictionary include `\,`, `\quad`, `\:`, `\qquad`, `\enspace`, `\!`. Identifying the specific token type based solely on the image is very difficult and also not truly necessary. Therefore, we proposed converting all whitespace token types to a single type: the `\,` token.
4. **Observation 4:** According to the KaTeX dictionary, we found that in LaTeX, there exist multiple ways to represent the same font type. Some font styles commonly used in mathematical expressions include `\mathrm`, `\mathtt`, `\mathfrak`, `\mathcal`. For example, `\mathrm`, `\rm`, and `\textrm` all produce the same output. Therefore, tokens of the same type can be normalized to a single form — in the case of the above example, we normalized to the `\mathrm` token.
5. **Observation 5:** In the list of bracket token types supported by LaTeX, we found overlaps. In practice, observing the IM2LATEX dataset, we found many cases where same-type bracket pairs were not yet normalized. For example, from the KaTeX dictionary, the `\vert` token and the `|` token are equivalent, and the `\lbrack` token and the `[` token represent the same mathematical symbol.

Before performing normalization, we need to tokenize the LaTeX sequences, i.e., split the LaTeX sequences into meaningful tokens, since the tokens in raw LaTeX expressions are typically written contiguously. We used the same approach as in [6] for tokenizing LaTeX sequences. After tokenization, based on the above observations combined with the cases presented in Table 6.1, we performed normalization on the dataset of 1,622,837 expressions.

6.2.4 Image Rendering

After normalizing the data for consistency, the next step in the process is to render the LaTeX sequences into images. The image rendering pipeline is performed with the following steps:

1. Save the mathematical expression as a .tex file by inserting the expression into a LaTeX source template as shown in Listing 6.1.
2. After obtaining the .tex file of the expression, compile it to PDF format using the pdfLaTeX⁷ compiler with the following command:

```
pdflatex -interaction=nonstopmode <output directory> >/dev/null.
```

Compilation sometimes fails because some tokens in the expression are not supported by pdfLaTeX; in such cases, these incompilable expressions are skipped.

3. Finally, use the ImageMagick⁸ library to convert the PDF file to PNG image format with the following command:

```
convert -density 200 -colorspace gray <PDF> -quality 100 <PNG>.
```

The generated expression images are in grayscale format, not RGB.

```
1 %\documentclass[varwidth]{standalone}
  \usepackage{amsmath, amssymb}
3 \usepackage{graphicx}
  \usepackage[active, tightpage, displaymath, textmath]{preview}
5 \begin{document}
  \thispagestyle{empty}
7 \newlength{\mylength}
  [put math expression here]
9 \end{document}\textbf{}
```

Listing 6.1: LaTeX source template for containing the mathematical expression to be rendered

After completing image generation, we performed image preprocessing. The task involves cropping excess white regions from the images and padding along the height and width so that the final image dimensions are divisible by 32, following the approach used by the IM2LATEX-100K dataset authors.

At the end of the image rendering process, the number of image-LaTeX sequence pairs obtained was 1,147,321 out of the initial 1,622,837 expressions.

6.2.5 Post-Processing

The post-processing step was proposed for the following purposes:

⁷<https://www.math.rug.nl/~trentelman/jacob/pdflatex/pdflatex.html>

⁸<https://imagemagick.org/index.php>

- To verify the consistency of the dataset once more, ensuring the normalization process was effective. In cases where data samples with unnormalized tokens still exist, normalization is performed.
- To check the vocabulary extracted from the dataset against the KaTeX dictionary to ensure that important tokens appear with sufficient frequency. We defined that each token must have a frequency of at least 1% of the total frequency of all tokens in the dataset. This ensures the diversity criterion we established. Tokens evaluated as important, according to our definition, are those categorized into the **Binary Operators**, **Relations**, and **Greek Letters** groups in the KaTeX dictionary — i.e., tokens that serve as operands or operators in expressions. If tokens belonging to these groups do not meet the frequency requirement, we duplicate data samples containing those tokens into new samples and perform minor modifications such as changing digits in the range $[0,9]$ or alphabetic letters to avoid duplication with the original samples. These augmented data samples are rendered into images and added to the existing dataset.

At the end of the post-processing step, the result we obtained was 1,567,356 data samples.

6.3 Dataset Statistics and Evaluation

After completing all steps in the dataset construction pipeline, in this final step, we analyze and report statistics on the height, width, and LaTeX sequence length of the data samples, as well as compare with the IM2LATEX-100K dataset. Additionally, the dataset analysis process helps us remove outlier samples from the dataset.

The presentation order in this section is as follows:

1. Filtering and outlier removal.
2. Analysis and comparison with the IM2LATEX-100K dataset.

Figure 6.4: *Correlation between occurrence frequency and size groups in LIMD*

6.3.1 Filtering and Outlier Removal

We used two criteria to determine whether a data sample is an outlier: first, based on image size; second, based on token length.

Statistics from the dataset show a total of 436 different size groups and 257 frequency groups. Figure 6.4 shows that many size groups have fewer than 50 occurrences, with approximately 50 size groups appearing only once. We found that approximately 45% of size groups have fewer than 40 occurrences, accounting for about 0.11% of total samples in the LIMD dataset.

Based on this, we removed the outlier samples, resulting in 1,565,639 from the initial 1,567,356 samples. Next, we examined the token length factor.

For convenience in evaluation, we divided token lengths into length groups spaced 15 units apart. For example, the length group [45, 60) includes data samples with token lengths ranging from 45 to 59. Figure 6.5 shows the contribution in terms of sample count for each length group and the corresponding cumulative contribution. The contribution trend decreases as token length increases. We chose to remove length groups contributing less than 0.1% of the total existing samples.

The result of filtering by token length yielded 1,564,755 from the previous 1,565,639 samples, which is also the final size of the LIMD dataset.

Figure 6.5: *Percentage contribution of each length group in LIMD*

Figure 6.6: *Comparison of sample counts by height between LIMD and IM2LATEX-100K*

6.3.2 Analysis and Comparison with IM2LATEX-100K

Below are analyses we performed to compare with IM2LATEX-100K. The comparison criteria include image height in Figures 6.6 and 6.7, image width in Figures 6.8 and 6.9, token length in Figures 6.10 and 6.11, and supported vocabulary in Figures 6.12 and 6.13. It can be seen that LIMD data has greater diversity in size and higher complexity as reflected in the token length criterion. In terms of vocabulary size, LIMD has 639 unique tokens, while IM2LATEX-100K has 496 tokens.

To facilitate model training with the LIMD dataset, we split the dataset into three subsets: training set, validation set, and test set, with corresponding quantities

Figure 6.7: Differences in height distribution between LIMD and IM2LATEX-100K

Figure 6.8: Comparison of sample counts by width between LIMD and IM2LATEX-100K

shown in Table 6.3:

6.4 Summary

With the goal of building a new dataset that addresses the limitations of the IM2LATEX-100K dataset, we proposed a pipeline for constructing a new database including steps such as collection, filtering, normalization, image rendering, post-processing, and finally analysis and evaluation. The dataset we built using this pipeline ensures three criteria: consistency, diversity, and complexity. We named

Figure 6.9: Differences in width distribution between LIMD and IM2LATEX-100K

Figure 6.10: Comparison of sample counts by token length between LIMD and IM2LATEX-100K

the dataset Large Image to Markup Database, or LIMD for short.

Figure 6.11: Differences in token length distribution between LIMD and IM2LATEX-100K

Figure 6.12: Most frequently appearing tokens in LIMD

Table 6.3: LIMD dataset split

Subset	Number of samples
Training	1377601
Validation	61226
Test	125928
Total	1564755

Figure 6.13: *Most frequently appearing tokens in IM2LATEX-100K*

Chapter 7

Mathematical Expression Extraction System for Document Images

In this chapter, we present how we built a mathematical expression extraction system for document images. In addition to the goal of building a complete system usable in practice, integrating our proposed recognition model into the system also helps us verify the generalization capability for real-world cases, providing a more concrete perspective and plans for future accuracy improvements.

The contents of this chapter are presented in the following order:

1. System design overview.
2. Demo results.

7.1 System Design Overview

In this section, we present the system components and their operation in detail. The main contents of this section include:

1. System workflow.
2. Overview of the mathematical expression region detection model.

7.1.1 System Workflow

A complete mathematical expression extraction system requires two main functional blocks: first, the expression region detection block; and second, the mathematical expression recognition block.

Our system concept includes the following capabilities:

- Processing images containing only mathematical expressions.
- Processing a single document image.
- Processing a PDF file with multiple document pages.

Based on this concept, we proposed a mathematical expression extraction system with the execution flow shown in Figure 7.1. The processing steps of the system can be described as follows:

1. **Step 1:** Upload the file for extraction.
2. **Step 2:** Check whether the uploaded file is a document image or just a mathematical expression image. If it is only a mathematical expression image, perform the recognition block and proceed to Step 7; otherwise, proceed to Step 3.
3. **Step 3:** Check whether the file is in PDF format. If not, this is a single document page image; pass it through the expression region detection block and the recognition block, then proceed to Step 7. Otherwise, proceed to Step 4.
4. **Step 4:** Convert the PDF file into a list of image files.
5. **Step 5:** Extract one file from the list.
6. **Step 6:** Pass the image file through the expression region detection and recognition blocks. Check whether the list is empty. If empty, proceed to Step 7. Otherwise, return to Step 5.
7. **Step 7:** End the extraction process and display the results.

7.1.2 Mathematical Expression Region Detection Model

As mentioned in the introduction of this thesis, we focus on making proposals to improve the mathematical expression recognition block, which is considered to have

Figure 7.1: Flowchart describing the system workflow

higher complexity than the expression region detection block. For the expression region detection block, we chose to use the ScanSSD model [1] with source code and trained weights publicly available on GitHub¹.

A brief overview of the ScanSSD model and the reasons for our choice:

1. The ScanSSD model is built based on the SSD object detection model [12]. Similar to the YOLO model [65], these are single-stage models. In object detection, single-stage models are preferred due to their faster processing time compared to other approaches. However, according to the authors, unlike YOLO, SSD

¹<https://github.com/MaliParag/ScanSSD>

Figure 7.2: ScanSSD architecture [1].

Figure 7.3: SSD architecture for object detection [12].

uses multi-scale grid structures instead of just a single grid type, allowing SSD to allocate the role of each grid type for detecting objects of different sizes. Figure 7.3 illustrates the SSD architecture; SSD only requires an input image and corresponding box labels, and at each vector on the feature map, boxes of different sizes are used to identify objects. Leveraging the SSD concept, the authors proposed the ScanSSD architecture for mathematical expression region detection as shown in Figure 7.2.

2. Our choice of the ScanSSD architecture for the expression region detection block is also due to the fact that ScanSSD was trained by the authors on a large amount of data as shown in Figure 7.4, thereby ensuring generalization capability for other data samples. Additionally, the authors' provision of source code and trained weights increases reliability and saves time on reimplementation.

7.2 System Implementation Details

After completing the system operation design, we proceeded with the implementation. The main contents of this section include:

TABLE I: TFD-ICDAR2019v2 Collection Statistics.

	Docs (Pages)	Formulas		Total
		1 symbol	>1 symbol	
Training	36 (569)	7506	18947	26453
Test	10 (236)	2556	9350	11906

Figure 7.4: *Dataset statistics for training and evaluating ScanSSD [1].*

1. Languages and supporting libraries.
2. Tools, software support, and deployment.
3. User interface and system features.

7.2.1 Languages and Supporting Libraries

To implement the system, we used the following main technologies:

- Backend: We used the Python language along with the PyTorch deep learning library [66] to build the model prediction methods.
- Frontend: We used the Streamlit² library to design the features and define user interaction methods. Streamlit is an open-source library that allows rapid creation of web browser applications.

7.2.2 Tools, Software Support, and Deployment

1. **Git:** Git³ is a distributed version control system. With Git, code management and teamwork become simpler and more convenient. A distinguishing feature of Git is its ability to create separate branches, which provides advantages such as better and more flexible task organization when working on multiple tasks simultaneously.
2. **Docker:** Docker⁴ is a platform for developers and sysadmins to develop, deploy, and run applications with containers. It allows creating independent and isolated environments to launch and develop applications. When deploying to

²<https://docs.streamlit.io/>

³<https://git-scm.com/doc>

⁴<https://docs.docker.com/>

production systems, simply running the Docker container creates its own environment and installs the necessary packages for immediate launch.

7.2.3 User Interface and System Features

In this section, we illustrate the interface designs corresponding to each operation performed.

Application Interaction

Figure 7.5: Steps to perform prediction.

Startup Interface

Figure 7.6: System interface at startup.

File Upload Interface

Figure 7.7: *Interface when uploading a mathematical expression image.*

Figure 7.8: *Interface when uploading a document image.*

Aggregation Cross-Entropy for Sequence Recognition

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Abstract

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In this paper, we propose a novel method, aggregation cross-entropy (ACE), for sequence recognition from a brand new perspective. The ACE loss function exhibits competitive performance to CTC and the attention mechanism, with much quicker implementation (as it involves only four fundamental formulas), faster inference (back-propagation approximately $O(1)$ in parallel), less storage requirement (no parameter and negligible runtime memory), and convenient employment (by replacing CTC with ACE). Furthermore, the proposed ACE loss function exhibited two noteworthy properties: (1) it can be directly applied for 2D prediction by flattening the 2D prediction into 1D prediction as the input and (2) it requires only characters and their numbers in the sequence annotation for supervision.

Figure 1. Examples of sequence recognition and counting problems.

tributed in a specific spatial structure. For example, there are highly complicated spatial relations between adjacent characters in mathematical expression recognition [56, 57]. In paragraph-level text recognition, characters are generally distributed like in line [41, 58] whereas in irregular scene

misalignment between ground truth strings and attention predictions, especially on longer input sequences [55, 59]. Bai et al. [3] also argues that the misalignment problem can confuse and mislead the training process, and consequently make the training costly and degrade recognition accuracy. Although the attention mechanism can be adapted for 2D prediction problem, it turns out to be prohibitive in terms of memory and time consumption, as indicated in [41] and [58].

Compelled by the above observations, we propose a novel aggregation cross-entropy (ACE) loss function for the sequence recognition problem, as detailed in Fig. 2. Given the prediction of the network, the ACE loss consists of three simple stages: (1) aggregation of the probabilities for each category along the time dimension; (2) normalization of the accumulative result and label annotation as probability distributions over all the classes; and (3) computation between these two probability distributions using cross-entropy. The advantages of the proposed ACE loss function can be summarized as follows:

- Owing to its simplicity, the ACE loss function is much quicker to implement (four fundamental formulas), faster to infer and back-propagate (approximately $O(1)$ in parallel), less memory demanding (no parameter and basic runtime memory), and convenient to use (simply replace CTC with ACE), as compared to CTC and attention mechanism. This is illustrated in Table 5, Section 3.3, and Section 4.2.
- Despite its simplicity, the ACE loss function achieves competitive performance to CTC and the attention mechanism, as established in experiments of regular/irregular scene text recognition and handwritten text recognition problems.

expectation-maximization-based online CTC algorithm that allows RNNs to be trained with an infinitely long input sequence, without pre-segmentation or external reset. However, the calculation process of CTC is highly complicated and time-consuming, and it requires substantial effort to rearrange the feature map and annotation when applied to 2D problems [46, 3].

2.2. Attention mechanism

The attention mechanism was first proposed in machine translation [12, 23] to enable a model to automatically search for parts of a source sentence for prediction. Then, the method rapidly became popular in applications such as (visual) question answering [32, 53], image caption generation [50, 52, 51], speech recognition [2, 25, 24] and scene text recognition [59, 30, 19]. Most importantly, the attention mechanism can also be applied to 2D predictions, such as mathematical expression recognition [56, 57] and paragraph recognition [41, 58]. However, the attention mechanism relies on a complex attention module to fulfill its functionality, resulting in additional network parameters and runtime. Besides, missing or superfluous characters can easily cause misalignment problem, confusing and misleading the training process, and consequently degrading the recognition accuracy [30, 19].

3. Aggregation Cross-Entropy

Formally, given the input image Z and its sequence annotation S from a training set \mathcal{D} , the general loss function for the sequence recognition problem evaluates the probability of annotation S of length L conditioned on image Z

Figure 7.9: Interface when uploading a PDF file.

Figure 7.10: Interface when increasing the number of PDF pages. The number of pages to extract can be adjusted.

Extraction Result Display Interface

Predicted LaTeX	Rendered Image	Cropped Image
$\overline{d} = -\sigma q^N (\Lambda d - q\lambda U \Delta),$	$\bar{d} = -\sigma q^N (\Lambda d - q\lambda U \Delta),$	$\bar{d} = -\sigma q^N (\Lambda d - q\lambda U \Delta),$
$\hat{\xi}^i = \sigma q^N \Lambda (\xi^i + q^i)$	$\hat{\xi}^i = \sigma q^N \Lambda (\xi^i + q^i)$	$\hat{\xi}^i = \sigma q^N \Lambda (\xi^i + q^i)$
$\xi^i = \bar{\sigma} q^N \bar{\Lambda} (\bar{\xi}^i + q^i)$	$\xi^i = \bar{\sigma} q^N \bar{\Lambda} (\bar{\xi}^i + q^i)$	$\xi^i = \bar{\sigma} q^N \bar{\Lambda} (\bar{\xi}^i + q^i)$
$d_i = \frac{1}{2}(d - \bar{\sigma} \bar{d}) = \frac{1}{2}((1 + q^N \Lambda) d$	$d_i = \frac{1}{2}(d - \bar{\sigma} \bar{d}) = \frac{1}{2}((1 + q^N \Lambda) d$	$d_i = \frac{1}{2}(d - \bar{\sigma} \bar{d}) = \frac{1}{2}((1 + q^N \Lambda) d$
$: \xi^j$	$: \xi^j$	$: \xi^j$
$l^{-1} \lambda x^i d - q^{1-N} \lambda U \hat{\theta}^i$	$l^{-1} \lambda x^i d - q^{1-N} \lambda U \hat{\theta}^i$	$l^{-1} \lambda x^i d - q^{1-N} \lambda U \hat{\theta}^i$
$+ \lambda q x^i \bar{d} + q^3 \lambda \bar{U} \bar{\theta}^i.$	$+ \lambda q x^i \bar{d} + q^3 \lambda \bar{U} \bar{\theta}^i.$	$+ \lambda q x^i \bar{d} + q^3 \lambda \bar{U} \bar{\theta}^i.$

Figure 7.11: Interface displaying prediction results for a single image. There are 3 columns: (1) Predicted LaTeX sequence, (2) Image rendered from (1), (3) Image cropped by the detection block.

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Predicted LaTeX	Rendered Image	Cropped Image
$\mathbf{c}_t = \sum_{i=1}^I \alpha_{ti} \mathbf{h}_i,$	$\mathbf{c}_t = \sum_{i=1}^I \alpha_{ti} \mathbf{h}_i,$	$\mathbf{c}_t = \sum_{i=1}^I \alpha_{ti} \mathbf{h}_i,$
$e_t = f(\mathbf{s}_{t-1}, \mathbf{h}_t) = \mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{u}_t$	$e_t = f(\mathbf{s}_{t-1}, \mathbf{h}_t) = \mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{u}_t$	$e_t = f(\mathbf{s}_{t-1}, \mathbf{h}_t) = \mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{u}_t$
$\mathbf{s}_t = LSTM(\mathbf{y}_{t-1}, \mathbf{c}_t, \mathbf{s}_{t-1}).$	$\mathbf{s}_t = LSTM(\mathbf{y}_{t-1}, \mathbf{c}_t, \mathbf{s}_{t-1}).$	$\mathbf{s}_t = LSTM(\mathbf{y}_{t-1}, \mathbf{c}_t, \mathbf{s}_{t-1}).$
$\alpha_{ti} = \frac{\exp(e_{ti})}{\sum_{k=1}^I \exp(e_{tk})}$	$\alpha_{ti} = \frac{\exp(e_{ti})}{\sum_{k=1}^I \exp(e_{tk})}$	$\alpha_{ti} = \frac{\exp(e_{ti})}{\sum_{k=1}^I \exp(e_{tk})}$

Figure 7.12: Interface displaying prediction results for a multi-page PDF file. Tabs appear to display results for each page.

7.3 Demo Results

Based on the workflow shown in the flowchart in Figure 7.1, there are three scenarios that users can perform when interacting with the system. We simulated these scenarios to evaluate the obtained results.

7.3.1 Scenario 1 — Image Containing Only a Mathematical Expression

Predicted LaTeX	Rendered Image	Cropped Image
$\Delta \equiv \frac{8\pi G_D f_H^2 - d + 2}{r_H} - \frac{2 \Lambda - 4\pi G_D (1 - f_H^2)^2}{p + d - 1} r_H.$	$\Delta \equiv \frac{8\pi G_D f_H^2 - d + 2}{r_H} - \frac{2 \Lambda - 4\pi G_D (1 - f_H^2)^2}{p + d - 1} r_H.$	$\Delta \equiv \frac{8\pi G_D f_H^2 - d + 2}{r_H} - \frac{2 \Lambda - 4\pi G_D (1 - f_H^2)^2}{p + d - 1} r_H.$

Figure 7.13: Results obtained for Scenario 1.

Predicted LaTeX

```
r = \left( \frac{m + E + k}{m + E - k} \right) e^{-2ikL}
```

Rendered Image

$$r = \left(\frac{m + E + k}{m + E - k} \right) e^{-2ikL \frac{B}{A}}, \quad t = e^{-2ikL \frac{d_1}{A}}$$

Cropped Image

$$r = \left(\frac{m + E + k}{m + E - k} \right) e^{-2ikL \frac{B}{A}}, \quad t = e^{-2ikL \frac{d_1}{A}}$$

Figure 7.14: Another illustration example for Scenario 1.

7.3.2 Scenario 2 — Image of a Complete Document Page

a precise order of integration has been taken [?]. The application of the theorem of [?, ?, ?] to this case must be seen as a redefinition of the integral on the planar region $S = \{\tau | \tau_2 > 0, -\frac{1}{2} \leq \tau_1 < \frac{1}{2}\}$ [?] in a way consisting in mapping the region $\{S - F\}$ into F an infinite number of times plus a prescription about how to integrate over a neighborhood of infinity in each of these infinitely many copies of F . So we have an infinite number of changes of variables (labeled by a couple of coprime integer numbers) and a prescription that by inverting the mappings would correspond to a way of integrating in the vicinity of zero. The validity of these changes of variables depends on the behaviour of the integrand on the left hand side of the equation (??) as a function of the modular parameter. From the modular invariance of $j(\tau)$ one can conclude that when $R > 1$ the integrand is regular (bounded) at zero. Therefore this complicated way of obtaining the integral over S will give the Riemann integral which is equal to the iterated integration at least in the region in which $R > 1$. Furthermore, the fact that we know that $\tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)$ has only one singular point means that $\tilde{\Lambda}_1(R) = \tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)$ for $R \geq R_0$. Taking this together with (??) we get that $\tilde{\Lambda}_1(R) > \tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)$ for $R < R_0$.

4 Conclusions

We have shown that the description of string theories as collections of fields breaks down when the typical length of the target space is smaller than the Planck length, $\sqrt{\alpha'}$. In the cases we have treated the physical explanation for this phenomenon can be enlightened by seeing that equation (??) is equivalent to knowing when

$$M(R) =: \int_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{d^2\tau}{\tau_2^2} J(\tau) \sum_{m,n \in \mathbb{Z}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{2\pi R^2}{\tau_2} |m\tau + n|^2 \right\} \stackrel{?}{=} 0 \quad (22)$$

where $J(\tau) = j(\tau) - 744$. We have proven that this integral vanishes when $R \geq R_0$ and, by duality symmetry that

$$M(R) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2R^2}\right) \frac{24\pi}{3} \quad R \leq R_0 \quad (23)$$

Moreover, the jump of the first derivative at R_0 can be easily seen equal to $16\pi/R_0$ as computed in section 2. For all of our examples this stems from the fact that duality in addition with the description of the string as a collection of quantum fields gives the partition function as a function of R for all $R > 0$.

Physically, $M(R)$ when $R \geq R_0$ would measure the quantum-field degrees of freedom of the model resulting from taking the left-moving part of the bosonic string after compactifying it using the Leech lattice [?] and modding out the states at the massless level [?, ?]. In other words, $M(R)$ measures nothing from a quantum-field theoretical point of view. However in [?] it has been shown that $J(\tau)$ is the partition function corresponding to a string realization

Figure 7.15: Image to be extracted 1.

<code>R > 0</code>	$R > 0$	$R > 0$
<code>R \, > \, \, 1</code>	$R > 1$	$R > 1$
<code>R \geq 5</code>	$R \geq 5$	$R \geq .$
<code>R > 1</code>	$R > 1$	$R > 1$
<code>\circ\tilde{\Lambda}_1(R) > \tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)</code>	$\circ\tilde{\Lambda}_1(R) > \tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)$	$\tilde{\Lambda}_1(R) > \tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)$
<code>< R_0</code>	$< R_0$	$< R_0$
<code>\tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)</code>	$\tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)$	$\tilde{\Lambda}_2(R)$
<code>M(R) = (1 - \frac{1}{2})</code>	$M(R) = (1 - \frac{1}{2})$	$M(R) = (1 - \frac{1}{2})$
<code>M(R)</code>	$M(R)$	$M(R)$
<code>R \geq R_0</code>	$R \geq R_0$	$R \geq R_0$
<code>(\frac{\pi R^2}{\tau_2} m\tau + n ^2) \stackrel{?}{=} 0</code>	$(\frac{\pi R^2}{\tau_2} m\tau + n ^2) \stackrel{?}{=} 0$	$(\frac{\pi R^2}{\tau_2} m\tau + n ^2) \stackrel{?}{=} 0$
<code>\sqrt{\alpha'}</code>	$\sqrt{\alpha'}$	$\sqrt{\alpha'}$

Figure 7.16: Results obtained on Image 1.

4 Asymptotics of the correlation functions

In this section we shall obtain the correlation functions of the models (7)-(10) in the asymptotic series form. The most important correlators are density-density correlator $H(x) = \langle \rho(x)\rho(0) \rangle$, $\rho(x) = \psi^*(x)\psi(x)$ being the density operator, and the one-particle density matrix $S(x) = \langle \psi^*(x)\psi(0) \rangle$. In the spin chain the similar objects are $H(x) = \langle \sigma_x^3 \sigma_1^3 \rangle$ and $S(x) = \langle \sigma_x^+ \sigma_1^- \rangle$, with $\sigma^\pm = \sigma^1 \pm i\sigma^2$.

The operators $\psi(x)$, $\rho(x)$ have no definite conformal dimensions, since they do not behave properly under conformal transformations. Nevertheless, they are local operators and, as such, can be represented as linear combinations of the primary and descendant operators. For simplicity, we write this sum at the moment rather symbolically without accounting of the “descendant contributions” (their role will be discussed below). As we shall see, to obtain the leading asymptotics it is sufficient to take into account only the primary operator contributions. Then, the general expression for a local operator $\hat{O}(x)$ has a form

$$\hat{O}(x) = \sum_{\phi} C_{\phi} \exp(iP_{\infty}^{\phi}x)\phi(x), \quad (42)$$

where the sum runs over primary operators ϕ and C_{ϕ} are some numerical coefficients. A possible gap in the momentum spectrum leads to appearance of the oscillating factors $\exp(iP_{\infty}^{\phi}x)$ in this formula. To find the correlation functions of the type $\langle \hat{O}(x)\hat{O}(y) \rangle$ it is sufficient to calculate pair correlators of primary operators ϕ by using the well-known technique of conformal field theory [10,33]. The most convenient way to do this is to represent primary fields in the exponential form (24) and to average their products by performing the conventional Gaussian functional integrals with the action (23).

The coefficients C_{ϕ} are non-zero if $\langle vac|\hat{O}(x)|\phi \rangle \neq 0$ in the thermodynamic limit (here $\langle vac|$ is the physical vacuum; for brevity sometimes we merely use the brackets to denote the physical vacuum expectation value). For example, the results of the previous section yield the following series (for Bose statistics):

$$\psi_B(x) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} c_m \cdot \exp(2\pi i \rho m x) \phi_{1,m}(x), \quad (43)$$

Figure 7.17: Image to be extracted 2.

Predicted LaTeX	Rendered Image	Cropped Image
<code>\psi_B(x) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} c_m \exp(2\pi i \rho m x)</code>	$\psi_B(x) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} c_m \cdot \exp(2\pi i \rho m x) \phi_{1,m}(x)$	$\psi_B(x) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} c_m \cdot \exp(2\pi i \rho m x) \phi_{1,m}(x)$
<code>[UNK] \langle \text{vac} \hat{O}(x) \phi \rangle \neq 0</code>	$[UNK] \langle \text{vac} \hat{O}(x) \phi \rangle \neq 0$	$\langle \text{vac} \hat{O}(x) \phi \rangle \neq 0$
<code>\langle \hat{O}(x) \hat{O}(y) \rangle</code>	$\langle \hat{O}(x) \hat{O}(y) \rangle$	$\langle \hat{O}(x) \hat{O}(y) \rangle$
<code>S(x) = \langle \sigma_x^+ \sigma_x^- \rangle</code>	$S(x) = \langle \sigma_x^+ \sigma_x^- \rangle$	$S(x) = \langle \sigma_x^+ \sigma_x^- \rangle$
<code>\psi(x)</code>	$\psi(x)$	$\psi(x)$
<code>\hat{O}(x)</code>	$\hat{O}(x)$	$\hat{O}(x)$
<code>\hat{O}(x) = \sum_{\phi} C_{\phi} \exp(i P_{\phi}^0 x) \phi(x)</code>	$\hat{O}(x) = \sum_{\phi} C_{\phi} \exp(i P_{\phi}^0 x) \phi(x)$	$\hat{O}(x) = \sum_{\phi} C_{\phi} \exp(i P_{\phi}^0 x) \phi(x)$
<code> \psi(0)\rangle</code>	$ \psi(0)\rangle$	$ \psi(0)\rangle$
<code>\pm i \sigma^2</code>	$\pm i \sigma^2$	$\pm i \sigma^2$
<code>\rho(x)</code>	$\rho(x)$	$\rho(x)$
<code>S(x) = \langle \psi^*(x) \rangle</code>	$S(x) = \langle \psi^*(x) \rangle$	$S(x) = \langle \psi^*(x) \rangle$

Figure 7.18: Results obtained on Image 2.

7.3.3 Scenario 3 — Multi-Page PDF File

Fig. 1. Attention-based encoder-decoder architecture for HTR.

column of the feature map corresponds to a receptive field on the transformed input image. Columns in the feature map are in the same order as receptive fields on the image from left to right [19].

Sequence modeling stage. The features \mathbf{V} from the feature extraction stage are reshaped into sequences of features \mathbf{H} , where each column in a feature map $\mathbf{v}_i \in \mathbf{V}$ is used as a sequence frame [19]. A bidirectional LSTM (BLSTM) is used for sequence modeling which allows contextual information within a sequence (from both sides, one forward and one backward) to be captured, and renders the recognition of character sequences simpler and more stable as compared to recognizing each character independently. For example, a contrast between the character heights in “il” can help recognize them correctly, as opposed to recognizing each character independently [19]. Finally, two BLSTMs are stacked to learn a higher level of abstractions. Dimensions of output feature sequence are 256×26 .

Prediction stage. An attention-based decoder is used to improve character sequence predictions. The decoder is a unidirectional LSTM and attention is content-based. The prediction loop has T time steps, which is the maximum length of a predicted word. At each time step $t = 1..T$ the decoder calculates a probability distribution over the character set

$$y_t = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{W}_0 s_t + \mathbf{b}_0)$$

where \mathbf{W}_0 and \mathbf{b}_0 are trainable parameters and s_t is a hidden state of decoder LSTM at time t . A character with the highest probability is used as a predic-

Figure 7.19: First page of the PDF file.

Figure 7.20: Prediction results for the first page.

tion. The decoder can generate sequences of variable lengths, but the maximum length is fixed as a hyper-parameter. We used the maximum length of 26 characters, including an end-of-sequence (EOS) token that signals the decoder to stop making predictions after EOS is emitted. The character set is also fixed. A case-insensitive model used further in experiments uses an alphanumeric character set of length 37, which consists of 26 lower-case Latin letters, 10 digits, and an EOS token. A character set of a case-sensitive model also includes 26 upper-case Latin letters and 32 special characters (`~\^#\%&'()*+,-./::<=>?@|_{|}`), and has a total length of 95 characters.

A hidden state of the decoder LSTM s_t is conditioned on the previous prediction y_{t-1} , a context vector c_t and a previous hidden state

$$s_t = LSTM(y_{t-1}, c_t, s_{t-1}).$$

A context c_t is calculated as a weighted sum of encoded feature vectors $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_J$ from the sequence modeling stage as

$$c_t = \sum_{i=1}^J \alpha_{ti} \mathbf{h}_i,$$

where α_{ti} are normalized attention scores, also called attention weights or alignment factors, and are calculated as

$$\alpha_{ti} = \frac{\exp(e_{ti})}{\sum_{k=1}^J \exp(e_{tk})},$$

where e_{ti} are attention scores calculated using Bahdanau alignment function [2]

$$e_{ti} = f(s_{t-1}, \mathbf{h}_i) = \mathbf{v}^T \tanh(\mathbf{W}s_{t-1} + \mathbf{V}\mathbf{h}_i + \mathbf{b}),$$

where \mathbf{v} , \mathbf{W} , \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{b} are trainable parameters.

Transfer learning. Transfer learning is used in this work to resolve the problem of insufficient training data. In general, it relaxes the assumption that the training and test datasets must be identically distributed [22] and tries to transfer the learned features from the source domain to the target domain. The source domain here is STR, and the target domain is HTR. This paper uses the strategy of fine-tuning [22] by initializing the weights from a pre-trained model and continuing the learning process by updating all 49.6M parameters in it. The architecture of the fine-tuned model is the same as that of the pre-trained model. This, together with a significant overlap between the source and the target domains (synthetic scene text and handwritten text), allows the use of training datasets that are relatively small in size (up to 213K), compared to the training dataset used to obtain the pre-trained model (14.4M).

The learning rate is an important parameter to consider in fine-tuning [14], and its impact on the results is examined. A high learning rate can make the model perform poorly by completely changing the parameters of a pre-trained

Figure 7.21: Second page of the PDF file.

Predicted LaTeX	Rendered Image	Cropped Image
$\mathbf{c}_t = \sum_{i=1}^J \alpha_{ti} \mathbf{h}_i$	$\mathbf{c}_t = \sum_{i=1}^J \alpha_{ti} \mathbf{h}_i$	$\mathbf{c}_t = \sum_{i=1}^J \alpha_{ti} \mathbf{h}_i$
$e_{ti} = f(s_{t-1}, \mathbf{h}_i)$	$e_{ti} = f(s_{t-1}, \mathbf{h}_i) = \mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{t}_i$	$e_{ti} = f(s_{t-1}, \mathbf{h}_i) = \mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{t}_i$
$s_t = LSTM(y_{t-1}, \mathbf{c}_t, s_{t-1})$	$s_t = LSTM(y_{t-1}, \mathbf{c}_t, s_{t-1})$	$s_t = LSTM(y_{t-1}, \mathbf{c}_t, s_{t-1})$
$\alpha_{ti} = \frac{\exp(e_{ti})}{\sum_{k=1}^J \exp(e_{tk})}$	$\alpha_{ti} = \frac{\exp(e_{ti})}{\sum_{k=1}^J \exp(e_{tk})}$	$\alpha_{ti} = \frac{\exp(e_{ti})}{\sum_{k=1}^J \exp(e_{tk})}$

Figure 7.22: Prediction results for the second page.

7.4 System Evaluation

1. **Strengths:** The system is capable of extracting expressions from diverse input types including expression images, document images, and multi-page PDF

files. The system interface is simple to operate and can display rendered images alongside original images for user comparison. Additionally, our proposed recognition model combined with the ScanSSD detection model shows relatively good results across the simulated scenarios, demonstrating the system's practical applicability.

2. **Weaknesses:** The current system has not been deployed to production infrastructure. Additionally, the system currently only supports basic extraction features and lacks features such as result editing support, result storage, and user account setup. Furthermore, due to training dataset limitations, the recognition model still has suboptimal results on multi-line expression images, limiting applicability in more complex cases.

7.5 Summary

In this chapter, we designed and built a mathematical expression extraction system for document images with complete basic features. The system demonstrates effectiveness when predicting on arbitrary document images. However, to be applicable in practice, the system still needs additional supplementary features, as well as improved model performance for complex cases such as multi-line expressions, matrix expressions, and systems of equations.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

8.1 Achievements

Throughout the process of completing this thesis, we achieved the following results:

- Surveyed the history and development of methods used to solve the MER problem.
- Researched and proposed a novel model that effectively solves the MER problem. The model, named Hybrid Vision Transformer, is based on the idea of using the ViT architecture to model global contextual information of expressions.
- Conducted a series of experiments and analyses to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method on the IM2LATEX-100K dataset.
- Constructed the **L**arge **I**mage to **M**arkup **D**atabase (LIMD) with the hope of advancing research on the MER problem.
- Completed a mathematical expression extraction system using the proposed model combined with an existing expression region detection model. The system is capable of extracting expressions and rendering them as images, and works well on PDF documents.

8.2 Limitations

- The proposed model still has significant limitations with multi-line expression types such as matrices and systems of equations. This is due to the training dataset having relatively few samples with similar characteristics.
- Due to resource and time constraints, we did not have the opportunity to conduct experiments on the proposed dataset.
- The current system only supports the most basic features of a mathematical expression extraction system and lacks supplementary features such as result editing support, query storage, and a user account management system.

8.3 Future Work

Based on the limitations presented above, we plan to continue developing this topic in the following directions:

1. Research methods to incorporate knowledge about the grammar and hierarchical nature of the LaTeX language into the proposed model, enabling the model to better predict complex cases.
2. Conduct experiments on the proposed dataset and perform evaluations on complex cases to verify the effectiveness of the dataset.
3. Add new features to the system, as well as deploy the system on cloud platforms for practical use.

Chapter 9

List of Publications

International Conferences

- Le, A. D., Pham, V. L., Ly, V. L., Nguyen, N. Q., Nguyen, H. T., & Tran, T. A. (2022, November). A Hybrid Vision Transformer Approach for Mathematical Expression Recognition. *In 2022 International Conference on Digital Image Computing: Techniques and Applications (DICTA) (pp. 1-7)*. IEEE. (Core: B)
- Nguyen, N. Q., Le, A. D., Lu, A. K., Mai, X. T., & Tran, T. A. (2023, August). Formerge: Recover Spanning Cells in Complex Table Structure Using Transformer Network. *In International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (pp. 522-534)*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. (Core: A)

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